
AGGREGATION MATTER
GALAXIES AND UNIVERSE DYNAMIC
EXPANSION UNIVERSE
SHRODINGER AND DIRAC EQUATIONS

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Matter Aggregation

Any aggregation or grouping of matter begins with an instability in the dynamics of a group of particles; if there were no instabilities, any dynamics would be linear or laminar (very boring dynamics); instabilities produce or originate groupings of matter; the reasons behind these instabilities are of various kinds.

- *Aggregation by Viscosity*

It can see the accumulation of dust and lint at home, in a dispersion of tree leaf by the wind, in an accumulation of drop water in a flat plate, in clouds or plastics in sea:

The friction between particles is the responsible of these accumulations: that is: the Viscosity.

Even, it's possible to see the self-classification or self-ordination of different seeds types, by viscosity:

The same occur in “flock’s ice” in sea, petroleum-oil filaments in leaks or water in cascades:

A case very interesting for me, is the Article, write by: ([32] Tsuyoshi Inoue). This article-simulation was performed by Tsuyoshi Inoue, with the ATERUI supercomputer operated by the @prcnaoj_en.

It can be observed that the seeds (yellow) accumulate in groups. This is due to the friction between them (viscosity). If these seeds are in a garden with grass, the accumulation in groups does may be not occur: the distribution may be is uniform.

This is because the grass has a higher friction (or viscosity) or in general, different friction; this fact, have consequences (it will see these):

So, the environmental it's very important also.

The environmental have the conditions ideals for accumulations of people; may be that this accumulation is due to the same feelings (to be in beach....); or accumulations of seeds in step street:

A lightning is a trajectory that could be considered as a conditioned Brownian displacement. In the following image, it can see the influence of the rainwater (environmental) cascade on the path of the lightning, which follows the path of the water:

The same in the next image: the environmental, produce the aggregation (shadow / need of shadow):

It's been barely 15 minutes since I got up from walking my dogs and, being in a square, I started laughing (and also now....) when I found some piles of seeds on the grass:

When I saw them, I wondered if the 4 accumulations I saw and their relative position had anything to do with:

- The size of the seeds.
- The friction between them.
- The speed of the wind.
- The friction with the grass.
- The size of the clumps.
- Etc...

No. It has nothing to do with that.

At first, the seeds are rolling on the grass, and at a certain moment, for a reason that it's difficult to know..., one of them stops and drags more and more seeds to adhere to it, forming an accumulation or group.

Even well-defined accumulations of leaves can be seen along the street. The leaves themselves define the outline of the accumulation:

A typical case of the existence of main flow lines, currents or large turbulences, depending on the context where they are found or as a function of main flows is this:

Upper and lower turbulence, are created from a main flow that runs from right to left; the smaller the scale of analysis, the more and more through a CFD simulation, it is very easy to observe the creation of currents or turbulence, from others:

This is a case of the creation of large turbulences, but the same happens with small turbulences, originated by a larger one:

It's also possible to create turbulence, the upper one for example, from the lower one.

The particles with the same or similar viscosity tend to join (that occur also in humans....).

In the case of flock's birds, the friction force or Viscosity, work as feelings:

The governing equations or relations, between birds, in order to create the flocks:

- There is a "bird boss", which do the way.
- There is a cohesion or density or pressure between birds.
- The direction of displacement is " $\frac{\text{Pressure}}{\text{density}}$ (acceleration).
- Other law....

In the other hand, for example, in a discotheque (or beach before), the people is there because they to have a good time, and the place, is the right one for it. Is possible show the next images, about interfaces between fluids of different viscosity (sea water), creating filaments, accumulations or aggregations; this densities and viscosities different, may be produced also by different temperature, salinity, etc....:

Obviously, this aggregation by Viscosity, work in the galaxies formation and others events; but always work by friction.

About this aggregation origin, I want to simulate some examples in CFD, in order to extract, may be..., some conclusions; these conclusion, are thought to priori....:

- ➔ 1 fluid in movement (any movement) in a box; analyze aggregations or density variations by viscosity, density, combinations, etc.....

- 2 fluids in movement (any movement) in a box; analyze the aggregation or density variations by viscosity, density, combinations, etc....
-

- **Aggregation by others forces**

It's possible to do a group of "all forces in universe":

- Gravity (attraction):

Gravitational Force

$$F = G \frac{m_1 m_2}{r^2}$$

F = gravitational force
 m_1 = mass 1
 m_2 = mass 2
 r = distance between centers of mass
 G = $6.7 \times 10^{-11} \text{ N} \cdot \text{m}^2/\text{kg}^2$

- Electromagnetism (attraction and repulsion):

→ The "light" also can be push, and so, affect to dynamic particles.

- Weak nuclear force.
- Strong nuclear force.

Some of these forces, work in the galaxies or in spyder web formation, etc....; basically the gravity.

- **Aggregation by Low Pressure**

A zone with low pressure (in relation other zone near), attract particles or matter; the case of a zone with high pressure, repelled or push a particle:

A particular case is the creation of depression tube and vortices:

When a particle move, his path is a depression zone; this zone is an attractor for any particle around; this depression tubes, create vortices around:

This low pressure, is present also around every particle in displacement, so, others particles are attracted.

It's possible, create an analogy with the gravity: let a spacecraft around planet; he have a speed and the gravity force "suck" the spacecraft to planet; depending the distance, the gravity force and speed, the orbit will be different (Newton theory gravity); the trajectory will be also different depending of others forces as a viscosity or density:

- Some think important: the aggregation by viscosity, is similar or at least have the same origin, with the aggregation by low pressure: the particle path, produce also a low pressure zone. That is very important to know it: Article ([33] Roberto Camassa, Daniel M. Harris, Robert Hunt, Zeliha Kilic & Richard M. McLaughlin).

Analyzing these orbits around vortex center, it should be possible to know the vortex geometry, his force, his evolution, his combination, etc....

Some equations and relations about; “r” distance between air particle and vortex center, “v” speed particle, “P” pressure “attraction” center vortex, “G” constant vortex and “T” rotation period:

$$\text{circular - orbit} \rightarrow G \frac{m}{r^2} = m \frac{v^2}{r}$$

$$T = 2\pi \sqrt{\frac{r^3}{Gm}}$$

$$P = \frac{G}{r^2}$$

Let “m=1”:

$$F = G \frac{m}{r^2} = \frac{G}{r^2}$$

Calculating the velocity rotation by CFD simulation and trying that the same velocity is the result of Newton theory, is possible so, know “G”.

That is very very important.

If let Force by Newton = Force Centripetal, we can know the orbit behavior. That is: what is the “G” value for our case:

$$\frac{mMG}{r^2} = m \frac{v^2}{r} \quad G = \frac{v^2 r}{M}$$

$$\frac{MG}{r} = v^2$$

If “a” is the semi major axis (orbit), and “T” the period:

$$a = \sqrt[3]{\frac{GM T^3}{4 \pi^2}} \rightarrow \frac{a}{T} = \sqrt[3]{\frac{GM}{4 \pi^2}}$$

$$G = \frac{a^3 4 \pi^2}{M T^2}$$

There is a value very important for defining a vortex; that is named Vorticity; for calculating that:

1.

$$(\omega_y)_{i,j} = \frac{\Gamma_{i,j}}{4\Delta X \Delta Z}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
\Gamma_{i,j} = & \frac{1}{2}\Delta X(U_{i-1,j-1} + 2U_{i,j-1} + U_{i+1,j-1}) \\
& + \frac{1}{2}\Delta Z(W_{i+1,j-1} + 2W_{i+1,j} + W_{i+1,j+1}) \\
& - \frac{1}{2}\Delta X(U_{i+1,j+1} + 2U_{i,j+1} + U_{i-1,j+1}) \\
& - \frac{1}{2}\Delta Z(W_{i-1,j+1} + 2W_{i-1,j} + W_{i-1,j-1})
\end{aligned}$$

This last value of Circulation, is function of U and W, velocity in the two axis X and Z.

2.

Another method for calculating the vorticity, is based in displacement points in area:

$$\Gamma_1(P) = \frac{1}{N} \sum_S \frac{(PM \wedge U_M) \cdot z}{\|PM\| \cdot \|U_M\|}$$

$$\Gamma_2(P) = \frac{1}{N} \sum_S \frac{(PM \wedge (U_M - \bar{U}_P)) \cdot z}{\|PM\| \cdot \|U_M - \bar{U}_P\|}$$

Center vortex:

Where “P” is a fixed point in the measurement domain. “S” is a two-dimensional area surrounding “P”, referred to as the window size, whose size must be defined by the user. “N” is the number of data points (M) that are located within “S”, and “UM” is the velocity vector at point “M”.

Finally, “z” is a unit vector normal to the plane of measurement, and “Γ1” (or “Γ2”) is calculated for all points in the measurement domain and then used to determine the center of the vortex. For an ideal axisymmetric vortex, the maximum value of |Γ1| is 1. For each possible center position, the “Γ1” criterion calculates the degree to which the flow rotates around this point. In this work, near the vortex core, |Γ1| was found to reach values between 0.9 and 1.

The only difference between the “Γ1” and “Γ2” criteria is that the average velocity over the window, away. This takes into account any uniform flow within the plane of rotation. With this method, when |Γ2| is greater than approximately 2/π, P is assumed to represent a point in the vortex.

Finally, another method:

3.

The mathematical model for the flow velocity in the circumference θ -direction in the Lamb-Oseen vortex is:

$$V_{\theta}(r, t) = \frac{\Gamma}{2\pi r} \left(1 - \exp \left(-\frac{r^2}{r_c^2(t)} \right) \right)$$

with

- r = radius,
- $r_c(t) = \sqrt{4\nu t}$ = core radius of vortex,
- ν = viscosity, and
- Γ = circulation contained in the vortex.

The radial velocity is equal to zero. The associated vorticity distribution in the vortex filament o Core Vortex direction can be found with the curt:

$$\omega_z(r, t) = \frac{\Gamma}{\pi r_c^2(t)} \exp \left(-\frac{r^2}{r_c^2(t)} \right)$$

An alternative definition is to use the peak tangential velocity of the vortex rather than the total circulation:

$$V_{\theta}(r) = V_{\theta \max} \left(1 + \frac{1}{2\alpha} \right) \frac{r_{\max}}{r} \left[1 - \exp \left(-\alpha \frac{r^2}{r_{\max}^2} \right) \right]$$

Where $r_{\max}(t) = (\alpha^{0.5})r_c(t)$ is the radius at which “ v_{\max} ” is attained, and the number $\alpha=1.25643$, see Devenport et al. The pressure field simply ensures the vortex rotates in the circumferential direction, providing the centripetal force:

$$\frac{\partial p}{\partial r} = \rho \frac{V^2}{r}$$

- *Aggregation by Tension*

The surface tension is the force that exerts a fluid to not expand. Normally this concept applies only to liquids. But this concept, applied to any fluid, can be understood as the force that the molecules perform, not to expand.

In the case of matter (fluid) in space, the same concept can be understood as gravity, since the greater the gravity, the greater the force to be expanded.

There is an expression very important (general expression), in order to have a relation between surface tension, compressibility and density; that is (“ σ ” is a surface tension, “ K ” compressibility and “ ρ ” density):

$$\sigma \left(\frac{K}{\rho} \right)^{1/2} = \text{const} \tan t$$

This general relation is very important to understand the surface tension in liquids but also in gasses or matter (particles) in general.

This is the same as saying that the greater the density (if the temperature is greater, the density lower), the greater the surface tension or fluid tension:

Water

Temperature	Density	Surface Tension
0	999,8	0,0756
5	1000,0	0,0749
10	999,7	0,0742
15	999,1	0,0735
20	998,2	0,0728
25	997,0	0,0720

Compressibility and fluid tension are very close together.

It is also responsible for droplets breaking down or water accumulating in areas above a dry surface:

- *Fingers by Viscosity, Density, Gravity (force) and Tension-Expansion*

The generation of fingers as a geometry, it's a special dynamic or aggregation of particles.

In this aspect, it show some cases in order to understand every phenomenon; in each case, it's possible the participation of more than 1 origin: not important that.

Basically, the origin of any fingers, it's also a Instability; from this Instability, it create the finger.

Sample 1:

If there is a delay time between displacement molecules, lower, the viscosity is bigger; that is the case for Lava, as a flow:

Sample 2 (analogy):

In the end of this "front shape", it can see a parabolic velocity profile....It can see this "parabolic" velocity profile, in a people group walking in street (there are boundary layer in lateral walls):

Sample 3:

Other effect very important about the Viscosity, is that:

It is possible to see "filaments" or "fingers" in the front of fluid flow as a (very similar to lava) honey for example:

Sample 4:

This is an effect between 2 fluids, with different surface tensions; this dynamic are called Marangoni Effect.

Typical sample:

Wine is a special case, as it is mainly a mixture of alcohol and water. Due to capillarity, a thin film of wine tends to rise up the walls of the glass. As this happens, both the alcohol and the water evaporate, but the former evaporates more quickly (due to its lower boiling point and higher vapour pressure), so the liquid in the wall acquires a higher surface tension than that at the bottom of the glass (remember that water has a higher surface tension than alcohol). This causes more wine to rise up the walls (to decrease the gradient of surface tension formed), so that more liquid accumulates at the top of the walls, until eventually the other force present comes into action: the weight of the accumulated liquid overcomes and causes gravity to form those tears or fingers that slide down the walls of the glass.

Sample 5:

Other example: from “Instabilities”, is possible to generate fingers in beach, considering the sand as a solid:

Sample 6:

In the case of a surface with hot liquid, it is observed that instead of the liquid ascending uniformly, some "fingers" are formed:

Sample 7:

Other example: two fluids, one of them in the surface; by gravity (may be any force so), the light fluid, create a "fingers" toward down:

Sample 8:

The Dark Matter can be taken as a fluid of different Viscosity from the fluid that surrounds this Dark Matter and through which it moves. This difference in Viscosity and Density (and may be others factors), as it has already seen, produces a peculiar and special distribution, producing "fingers", voids, accumulations, groups, etc...

Sample 9:

The same occur in enormous blobs deep inside the Earth. It can just barely detect them using seismic imaging or Tomography, and it really don't know what they are:

- *Supernova expansion and Nebulae Bubbles*

As a sample and similarity with the reality (fingers), it shows a supernova explosion; it's possible to see the alterations in border: when a supernova explodes, it's always in a spherical direction. But depending on the density of the shock wave (also viscosity and more, and the environmental), even square geometries are formed; it's therefore possible to know this density variation in environmental, so that any geometry can be created; also depend of viscosity and superficial tension, between 2 fluids: environmental and star matter:

It's possible see the same effect, in others phenomena's:

Sample 1:

It's a sample, special; not are 2 fluids or 1 fluid on a solid....

Let's suppose that two apples collide with each other, at a speed of 90 km/h; you can see perfectly, the star structure of the skin when it explodes; the skin breaks, as it reaches its elastic limit (the surface solid of a apple, tend to expand and fill more surface....). The same applies to spherical nebulae: they are spherical until they reach a limit, from which small spheres form in the shock wave:

Sample 2:

It's a sample, special; not are 2 fluids or 1 fluid on a solid....

In the Article ([34] Asher P. Mouat, Clay E. Wood, Justin E. Pye, and Justin C. Burton), it is possible see the same effect, in a border of fluid in expansion:

Sample 3:

Lava explosion: the expansion is not uniform:

Sample 4:

In an experiment about 2 fluid shocks: it can also see the formation of "pearls" in fluid shock:

Sample 5:

Another example can be seen on a wet solid disc, in rotation. Perhaps the logical thing would be the water covering the surface should be diffused outwards in molecules.

But the density is finite... this makes that because of the viscosity and in this case the surface tension, the water groups in point and from these points, the water escapes:

This is the same reason why "pearls" are formed in a supernova explosion so.

So, there is a limit; firm this limit, there are the formation of sub-bubbles and crack of shock wave; this "crack" limit depends of ("fluid" in expansion and environmental):

- Viscosity.
- Density.
- Surface tension.
- Size.
- Speed of expansion.
- Others like temperature, pressure, etc..

The particles of a fluid with a higher viscosity will respond more quickly to the changes in the surrounding particles; therefore, when there are small fluctuations or instabilities, they drag particles.

But, there are, for example, Bubbles nebulas. Why it is possible?

As said before, a fluid in the form of a sheet, when expanded, groups together.

But we know, for example, bubble nebulae or soap bubbles: these keep the surface, until a certain moment. This fact has limitations or conditions.

In this case, the crack "limit", is not present "yet":

If some instant, the crack is overcome:

An analogy can be observed with a social fashion: fashion is advancing in Society, also advancing in Time, and there comes a moment, due to various reasons, when fashion, is divided into various fashions or trends.

Galaxies dynamic and high scale geometry universe

- *Galaxies: history vital*

The formation and evolution of a galaxy and galaxies can be simulated, assuming that it has working with a fluid with certain density, viscosity, etc.... conditions.

Obviously, the dynamics of galaxies is also determined by forces not related to fluid dynamics, such as gravity, electromagnetism, etc. What we are trying to do here is to give a view of the dynamics of galaxies, assuming that they behave like a fluid, inside other fluids.

Origin:

When a particle move, his path is a depression path or zone; all particles behind or around her, rotate around the depression tube, producing vortices:

These “paths” of low pressure or density, can help matter particles, to aggregate each and other, producing, in the future, stars, black holes, etc. That is: the galaxy seed. Also, these paths allow and help other’s galaxies behind to follow the first galaxy (galaxies group). It’s been barely 15 minutes since I got up from walking my dogs and, being in a square, I started laughing (and also now....) when I found some piles of seeds on the grass:

When I saw them, I wondered if the 4 accumulations I saw and their relative position had anything to do with:

- The size of the seeds.
- The friction between them.
- The speed of the wind.
- The friction with the grass.
- The size of the clumps.
- Etc...

No. It has nothing to do with that.

At first, the seeds are rolling on the grass, and at a certain moment, for a reason that it's difficult to know...., one of them stops and drags more and more seeds to adhere to it, forming an accumulation or group.

Creation and rotation:

May be, in the center of every galaxy, exist a black hole or not.

A Galaxy rotates, because the black hole or condensed matter in its center is most likely to rotate. This turn "drags" more and more matter, also making it rotate: for example, in the case of a sump, the water starts to rotate because it is most likely (it is very difficult not to rotate....). This rotation makes more and more water turn.

The same explanation it has for a water sink: the rotation direction (without Coriolis and more), is random; there are a rotational moment, add for every particle (star) which is pull.

Black holes may or may not form in the interior of a galaxy; a black hole may be the origin of a galaxy as explained above, but its existence is not necessary; there can be galaxies without a very massive black hole in their interior just fine.

The stars, or the galaxy in general, do not necessarily revolve around the massive black hole that may exist inside it; the gravity of that black hole, if it exists, is very little in relation to the gravity of the whole galaxy; its gravity "only" affects the stars around it; the galaxy revolves around a center of mass; in fact, the massive black hole, if it exists, may not necessarily be located around the center of the galaxy.

The aggregation matter origin:

- Created by Globular aggrupation (may be from an only one star....).
- Dust cloud (also by dark matter aggregation ?? $\dot{\iota}$).
- Depression tube.

-
- Friction or viscosity.
 - Black hole. This black hole, can be formed before (as a seed) or after galaxy.

Can be the globular cluster, the origin of every galaxy?: a globular cluster, have rotation (also, is the most likely....). Rotation velocity stars in globular cluster, with the rotation axis:

The old galaxies, are very irregular: 13-8 billion years old this galaxy-s light comes to us from when the Univers; these galaxies are very young and not big time for development:

More very old galaxies:

Structure formation: arms and more:

First of all, and obviously, it's possible appreciate the similarity with any real galaxy (geometry pattern – typical in mathematical or physical models). Typical galaxy in spiral:

Is possible so, apply fluids theory to galaxy formation, evolution and interaction? May be....

Other explanation, is more accurate and “real”, but complementary to these before: around a galaxy, there are a lot matter in different forms (in fact, the galaxies, swim in Dark Matter: the quantity of dark matter, is much bigger....): traditional or visible, dark matter, may be etc.... that is: the density and also the viscosity, around and into a galaxy, is big.

Imagine now, that it has a cloth and a cylinder placed in the central part which rotates, creating a special pattern (A rotating fluids set with different viscosities and densities, can generate arms, as a density contours). Zones of creation of galaxy arms; the same phenomenon in whirl water. Also is possible generate these “arms” in chocolate or coffee rotating.:

Suppose a coffee rotating in glass; it's possible in CFD, analyze the surface and show a “heights map-field” or density, forming the spiral as a galaxy arms:

Few weeks ago, I went to Amsterdam; in Nemo (Science Museum) I have seen a tool for generating spirals from fluids in rotation:

Now, I want to create some simulations in order to know better, all that:

- ➔ 1 Fluid in a disc in rotation; analyze the density variations, against viscosity, density, etc....
- ➔ More than 2 fluids in in rotation; analyze the density variations, against viscosity, density, etc....
- ➔

One the goals, it's may be, analyze the dependence of arms number against: Viscosity, density, velocity rotation.

These waves are zones low pressure and other's high pressure. In the zones of high pressure, so with high density, it creates the stars, so the arms (with the help, as always, of the gravity):

If instability occurs in a rotating star cloud, a zone or zones can form that corresponds to a zone of higher density (stars tend to cluster together); as they rotate, the arms appear. The initial instability is responsible for the origin of the arms:

This origin of arms from gravity waves, is the similar to generation of traffic jam from a instability created for one car in acceleration, or brake (soliton).

→ Any explanation for the creation or formation of arms in a galaxy is based on instability.

In fact, if a cup of coffee is moved and the spoon touches the surface, this contact is an instability that develops in the arms as the coffee continues to rotate. This instability, as always, is the most important in arm generation.

For example, in a galaxy in bar, in the zone “A” (extremes) is more likely the generation of arm, caused by:

- Drag matter for the rotation.
- Generation of instability in “A”.

In other galaxy or better: stars accumulation, is possible the creation of arms from instabilities (6 in this image sample):

It's not rare so, the result or conclusion (from Spitzer telescope and data in Gaia mission of ESA) about the "break" in one arm of milky way: it's perfectly possible a instability in this arm; this instability can produce this "break" or also the called "spur"; these spurs, are in 3D not only in the galaxy plane:

Other case: 2 "armless" galaxies can give rise to a single galaxy formed by several arms: 2 galaxies come together by the action of their gravities rotating around each other; by the action of the ram pressure, arms are formed in each of them which, when united, form the arms of the new galaxy:

Now. I want to create some simulations in order to know better, all that:

- ➔ 1 Fluid in a disc in rotation; analyze the density variations, against viscosity, density, etc.....: creating a instabilities.
- ➔ More than 2 fluids in in rotation; analyze the density variations, against viscosity, density, etc.....: creating a instabilities.
- ➔

One the goals, it's my be, analyze the dependence of arms number against: Viscosity, density, velocity rotation, instabilities (size, magnitude, number, etc....).

At certain heights in the atmosphere, there are different layers of air at different temperatures and therefore densities and viscosities. At that time, the interface, works like the free surface of the sea; waves with different frequencies and amplitudes are produced, producing different cloud geometries:

In the pick of every wave, there are more density, so in this zone, it's possible to aggregate the matter.

These waves are density waves. Why a lot are shapes types of galaxies? Depend of initial matter distribution, including amount, velocity rotation black hole, dimensions of black hole or disturbance zone, environmental, etc.... The galaxies matter may be composed by baryonic matter but also may be, by Dark Matter transformed in baryonic matter.... (Mond theory ????).... It's possible see the arms, through a density map or viscosity map-field generation (coffee or chocolate for example – is very complicate to see these densities variation or height variation - waves).

There are other methods for simulate a galaxy: creating a vortex as a galaxy. And more: the interaction between galaxies as a vortices.

It knows that a bullet before leaving for the rifle barrel rotates within the barrel. The goal is to provide rotation (inertia) to go "straight":

The bullet keeps rotating until it reaches its target.

The same happens when we throw a rugby ball: given its peculiar shape it must travel in this position with respect to the direction of the air.

Drag will be much smaller and therefore it may achieve greater distances. But to maintain this position it must rotate, and that's how it is thrown: in rotation:

Therefore, it can think of an alternative system, to generate high-energy rotational vortices, different to what we have seen up to now:

It can try to fold the airflow so that we keep the rotation applied previously.

This could be done by circulating air through a kind of auger, so that we force a spiral rotation:

When air circulates this device entirely we think that it will continue to maintain the rotation a certain distance after; however, this is completely wrong: just at the end of the auger its rotation is drastically and suddenly interrupted. It is always necessary to generate vortices due to a device that is based on pressure differences; why?

Because by this way, it produces a depression tube after system which suctions the air producing the vortex along the time: the translation of particle, produce the vortex.

We choice the method, placing a “wing” (there is a difference pressure so), in order to create a vortex:

First, it analyzes the next test:

- 1 Fluid.
- Wing in order to generate a vortex.
- Visualize the vortex, behind wing.

First image: blue-red → low-high pressure. Rest images: red-blue → high-low vorticity.

As a first test, good attempt....

It's necessary so, more, in order to create and visualize better the arms.

There is other way for creating a galaxy:

Is an idea from Marco Fedi, Mario R.L. Artigiani (with some variations for improving it); is a body, in rotation, with low pressure in center:

In the work of creators (Theoretical and CFD analysis of gravity and galaxy formation and rotation in a dilatant vacuum), the vortices is static; I propose simulate 2 or more vortices in order to analyze the interaction; for that, is necessary that the vortices, can move (in CFD that called 6-DOF or 6 freedom degrees).

It can make this body, with more than 2 walls, in order to create more than 2 arms for the galaxy. And more: in the center, it creates an outlet, and the mass trough that exit by outlet, is mass to add in center and so, more gravity or less pressure.

Also it's possible, to generate 2 black holes, and analyze the rotation between them, generating the gravitation waves:

- Success horizon against size and mass.
- Rotation or not.
- Velocity and sense rotation.
- Etc....

Phenomenons, properties, relation and interactions between, geometries, similarities:

All my life I have worked on aerodynamics applied especially to race cars.

For this reason, I have deeply studied the creation of vortices and the interaction between them.

The main objective is to apply this knowledge directly to the formation, evolution and interaction of galaxies. From this deep knowledge about vortices and turbulences in general, it's possible to know phenomena that will occur in galaxies, because they occur in vortices: formation, evolution and interaction.

Next, there are several phenomena that occur in vortices and that although they have not yet been observed in galaxies, surely they will occur. It's a matter of investigating such phenomena, and for that, I need time and means to do it.

a) LUMINOSITY / ROTATION VELOCITY

The galaxy matter in rotation, interaction with other matter, producing big greater densities zones. So, It's possible to think, that if a galaxy have a greater rotation velocity, the interaction with the matter, also is bigger, so more stars zones formation. So finally,

If a galaxy have a greater rotation velocity, its luminosity will may be bigger. And that is true. Classification galaxies luminosity, against rotation velocity; Rubin in 1983:

b) LUMINOSITY / TYPE

A galaxy has more luminosity, will must be more arms. Classification galaxies Sa, Sb and Sc.:

Rotation velocity “Sa”, “Sb” and “Sc” galaxies.

c) **GALAXIES TAIL**

When talking about the tail produced by a Galaxy on its way through the Universe, there are 2 types of Tails:

- The one produced by the stripper of the matter of the galaxy caused by Ram Pressure: high pressure.
- The galaxy, in its path, "cleans" the path, capturing matter and leaving a trace of low density: low pressure.

In one case, the Tail acts by repelling matter (if there is difference pressure and also may be attracting by gravity), and the second case, by attracting matter. The matter in a galaxy's path depends on whether the galaxy moves through more matter; in that case it will leave traces of itself combined with the surrounding matter due to Ram Pressure. In the case that there is hardly any matter in its path, it will drag what little matter there is or other types of interactions.

Sample about stripped galaxy and their CFD simulation:

More about stripped galaxies:

Simulation CFD by Rafael Ruggiero from Brasil:

More CFD simulation by ([35] Elke Roediger, Marcus Brüggem and Matthias Hoef):

The same occur in Mallorca Island (tail sand formation) in storm:

d) GALAXIES WITH LESS DARK MATTER

If there is little dark matter, the galaxy has fewer arms.

e) OLD GALAXIES AGAINST LUMINOSITY AND ROTATION VELOCITY

In the past (more density - far), a galaxy have more luminosity with less rotation velocity than today.

f) VELOCITY ROTATION AGAINST DISTANCE

Rotation velocity against distance:

Galaxy	RA hh mm ss	Dec dd mm ss	PA d	D Mpc	Type	m_{abs}	$\log D_{25}$	$\log v_n$
(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)	(8)	(9)
NGC 522	01 24 45.91	09 59 40.5	33.3	39.0	Sbc	-20.53	1.44	2.252
NGC 684	01 50 14.03	27 38 44.2	88.8	50.4	Sb	-21.53	1.53	2.368
MCG-01-05-047	01 52 49.01	-03 26 51.2	161.4	71.5	Sc	-21.77	1.47	2.410
NGC 781	02 00 09.02	12 39 21.5	13.0	49.8	Sab	-20.87	1.18	
NGC 2654	08 49 11.91	60 13 13.9	65.0	19.2	SBab	-20.09	1.62	2.295
UGC 4906	09 17 39.94	52 59 34.3	49.0	32.6	Sa	-20.26	1.30	2.228
NGC 2862	09 24 55.10	26 46 29.0	114.0	58.5	SBbc	-21.44	1.41	2.464
NGC 3279	10 34 42.61	11 11 50.7	152.0	19.9	Scd	-19.27	1.44	2.208
NGC 3501	11 02 47.35	17 59 22.6	28.0	16.2	Sc	-19.05	1.54	2.147
NGC 5981	15 37 53.55	59 23 30.9	139.5	36.1	Sc	-20.61	1.43	2.424
NGC 6835	19 54 33.09	-12 34 02.5	72.0	23.0	SBa	-19.55	1.38	1.803

D Mpc (5)	Type (6)	m_{abs} (7)	$\log D_{25}$ (8)	$\log v_m$ (9)
39.0	Sbc	-20.53	1.44	2.252
50.4	Sb	-21.53	1.53	2.368
71.5	Sc	-21.77	1.47	2.410
49.8	Sab	-20.87	1.18	
19.2	SBab	-20.09	1.62	2.295
32.6	Sa	-20.26	1.30	2.228
58.5	SBbc	-21.44	1.41	2.464
19.9	Scd	-19.27	1.44	2.208
16.2	Sc	-19.05	1.54	2.147
36.1	Sc	-20.61	1.43	2.424
23.0	SBa	-19.55	1.38	1.803

Analyze now, “D” and “V” relation. Relation between Rotation velocity against distance:

There is a relation lineal. Ok.....

g) VELOCITY ROTATION AGAINST MASS

Velocity rotation, against galaxy mass:

h) AGE AGAINST ARMS

There are a relation between galaxy age and arms (number arms, luminosity and rotation speed). That is: if the galaxy is older, the galaxy has more arms (also in general, obviously): Triangulum 2.38 to 3.07 Mly, Pinwheel 20.9 ± 1.8 Mly, M51 37 Mly:

That is “normal” because if it’s older, have more time to “work” with the environmental. A young galaxy, has less arms, is irregular and diffuse:

i) INTERACTION BETWEEN

A) INTERACTION AS A VORTICES WITHOUT GRAVITY

In the sky, it's possible to see, a lot samples of collisions:

When two galaxies collide, collide also the dark matter.

It's possible to see the same between hurricanes (analogy with fluid theory or geometries patterns):

So, it can think about (evolution and combination), as an interaction between fluids vortex. The interaction between vortices is some think very important and complicate:

These unions or alteration, depending of intensity (vorticity) of vortex; if there is one vortex, bigger than other vortex (red and green), can produce that: (each horizontal file correspond one context or size):

Also depend of densities, viscosities, temperatures, rotation direction, velocity rotation, size, etc.... and other's paths as a way of other galaxies (depression tubes):

The study of these interactions between vortices, is typical in aerodynamic work about Race Cars; is important create vortices, but is more important, their interactions. Vortices in front wing race car Formula 1:

In this typical case, there are lot samples of interaction between vortices with the same or different turn sense, sizes, velocity, etc.... (the same in galaxies). It could simplify the problem of the interaction of 2 or more galaxies, assuming it work in 2 dimensions, but this is not real. Galaxies are 3-dimensional and so is their location. Interactions are not executed in a plane. Galaxies, interact with each other, giving rise to many different geometric shapes, depending on several factors:

- speed of rotation.
- size.
- quantity of mass.
- 3D location.
- direction of rotation.
- direction translation.
- Etc.....

On the other hand, it is possible perfectly, to simulate the interactions between galaxies and also the formation of galaxies, by CFD Simulation:

B) SENSE ROTATION – 1 , INTERACTION

Article ([37] J. H. Lee et al):

The sense of rotation of a galaxy is influenced by the displacement of its companions, even the farthest. This is revealed by the CALIFA galactic survey data used by a group of astronomers to carry out the study.

In principle, distant companions, located millions of light years away, should show little influence on the shape and rotation of the central galaxy, but a recent study indicates that the direction of rotation of a given galaxy depends, in effect, on the average displacement of its neighbors, including those located at long distances.””

It can see another very illustrative effect of the importance of the density and viscosity and this last Article.

Let’s think of a submerged pendulum. It makes it swing.

It will be able to see that the pendulum will stop oscillating almost immediately. This is due to the opposition of the water molecules which act on it. In fact, the more density/viscosity the fluid has (less compressibility), the less time the initial oscillation will take to stop.

Now, let's think of two identical pendulums immersed in a fluid and with opposed oscillations.

After a short time, both pendulums will oscillate in the same direction and with the same frequency!!!

Why does this fact happen?

Because the density/viscosity of the fluid, because its variations and the forces transmission through the particles. On the moon, this wouldn't happen, due to the air absence.

This morning, walking with my mother, she said to me: we're going with the wrong step. In other words, we don't have the same footprint in the same instant. This makes the walk "unstable" and unpleasant....

C) SENSE ROTATION – 2, AS A GEARS

For 2 nearby galaxies (can also occur in more distant galaxies), they rotate in opposite directions. This is because, in their rotation, each galaxy drags its companion, like 2 gears (Magnus effect):

D) RESONANT ORBITS IN GALAXIES

Article: Francesca Fragkoudi: orbits of stars in a Milky Way-like barred spiral galaxy; these are resonant orbits extracted directly from one of the Auriga cosmological simulations, and shown in an inertial and rotating frame of reference:

E) MAGNUS EFFECT

There is an effect associated with the rotation of a galaxy; it is the Magnus effect. A galaxy is a group of matter or energy in general, rotating more or less compactly; this causes the galaxy to have a friction with the matter that “may exist” around it, in its path: more matter or density, more friction and more Magnus force; this density is energy density.

It can observe that there is no difference between the lines at the top and bottom part. Meaning: there is no difference of pressure. Wouldn't this also depend on the Reynolds number? For some transition Reynolds, we would have temporary behaviors, non-symmetric solutions which are known as the von Karman Street, but this is not the case that concerns us to understand the phenomenon.

Now, let's suppose that the same ball is rotating. There is, therefore, a perceptible difference of pressure on the top and bottom of the ball. The air goes from the left to the right in the image:

If it turns the ball in the direction indicated with the green arrow and if there is this difference of pressure, the ball will tend to go down: there is lower pressure below because the flow circulates quicker.

Depending on the direction in which the ball rotates, it will go up or down. In other words, the resultant force will have a determined direction, depending on the direction of the ball.

This friction between galaxy and matter, together with the direction of rotation, produces a force that makes the path tend to follow a specific path:

For example, in moon, is not possible doing an effect with football:

This effect is applied to low pressure tubes as a galaxies paths. So is very important in order to know the full interaction between galaxies.

F) GALAXIES: FULL INTERACTION

It's a set and consequence of all effects before. In this Article, it analyzes Navier Stokes Equations, from the simplest versions, analyzing term by term and ending with a full version introducing even the electromagnetic effects.

To "really" analyze the interaction of galaxies or the creation or formation of the Spider web of the universe, it's necessary to apply the more complicated Navier Stokes equations, since they reflect perfectly, what happens in reality.

Each galaxy or group of galaxies, like tail, leaves a path altered in density or pressure.

These "virtual" pathways are there and exist, but they are very difficult to locate and know but they are there, and they determine and modify the path of other galaxies that approach these pathways.

This path "virtual", is a factor very important in galaxies dynamic: the dynamic galaxy, produce an alteration in environmental.

Galaxy tails (high or low density), also evolve, move and change. The reason is that the environment affects them: other tails, zones of low and high density, etc....

The evolution of galaxies is based in:

- Viscosity.
- Interaction between Tails.
- Gravity.
- Others forces....

Here, an image very important: Star bridge in Magellanic clouds:

➔ It's possible to know what is the path or direction of displacement of each galaxy, studying the star bridges, tails, etc....

About this last affirmation or possible research, there is an Article very recent ([37] Ekta Patel and other's):

“With the release of Gaia DR2, it is now possible to measure the proper motions (PMs) of the lowest mass, ultra-faint satellites in the Milky Way's (MW) halo for the first time. Many of these faint satellites are posited to have been accreted as satellites of the Magellanic Clouds (MCs)”

From this Article, it's has a table of position and velocities of galaxies set, in order to analyze the interactions (in the past and the future) or paths between:

	X	Y	Z	V _x	V _y	V _z
	[kpc]	[kpc]	[kpc]	[km s ⁻¹]	[km s ⁻¹]	[km s ⁻¹]
Aqu2	28.71±1.23	53.16±1.77	-85.98±2.87	91.31±239.21	250.76±212.3	130.49±166.0
CanVen2	-16.37±0.22	18.58±0.51	158.67±4.32	-0.66±162.9	-203.05±150.42	-70.09±16.93
Car2	-8.3±0.0	-34.54±0.8	-10.65±0.25	134.12±11.0	-287.58±4.14	134.95±13.02
Car3	-8.29±0.0	-26.6±1.24	-8.06±0.37	-10.7±18.9	-151.85±8.41	356.05±25.9
Cra2	10.3±0.88	-81.23±3.86	75.13±3.57	-34.4±35.2	115.88±21.41	2.83±19.96
Dra2	-10.57±0.04	15.58±0.28	14.61±0.26	22.54±22.16	100.31±22.35	-341.04±25.48
Hor1	-7.16±0.1	-48.01±4.36	-67.91±6.16	-20.24±30.24	-150.18±45.34	152.34±32.09
Hyl1	1.87±0.19	-19.59±0.36	-16.48±0.3	-144.15±6.58	-178.7±8.73	288.26±8.57
Hya2	47.82±3.06	-117.14±6.39	76.34±4.17	-165.16±302.26	-92.01±257.22	208.27±275.52
Phx2	25.47±3.14	-24.81±2.31	-71.85±6.69	-67.68±48.82	-165.47±54.59	162.72±31.4
Ret2	-9.63±0.06	-20.38±0.96	-24.14±1.14	19.92±12.38	-96.74±17.42	218.24±14.63
Seg1	-19.38±0.98	-9.47±0.84	17.67±1.57	-98.19±18.34	-205.06±38.14	-35.49±22.9
Tuc3	0.79±0.41	-8.95±0.4	-19.03±0.85	23.48±5.94	146.27±8.05	185.68±5.69
Car1	-24.72±0.6	-94.62±3.48	-39.26±1.44	-36.84±18.42	-50.55±8.51	149.23±20.28
Dra1	-4.15±0.32	64.88±5.0	45.01±3.47	54.29±13.85	4.15±8.25	-151.78±11.73
Fnx1	-39.58±0.57	-48.15±0.87	-126.93±2.3	38.14±22.76	-107.56±21.25	76.0±9.72
Scu1	-5.22±0.19	-9.59±0.6	-84.12±5.26	16.93±12.7	175.89±16.04	-96.14±1.87
UMin1	-22.16±0.71	52.0±2.68	53.46±2.75	-4.26±10.75	46.77±10.69	-148.2±10.61
LMC	-1.06±0.33	-41.05±1.89	-27.83±1.28	-57.60 ±7.99	-225.96±12.60	221.16±16.68
SMC	15.05±1.07	-38.10±1.75	-44.18±2.03	17.66±3.84	-178.60±15.89	174.36 ±12.47

There is a "particular" type of vortex interaction, called Crow's Instability. I don't know why the "fashion" of naming many things, but Crow is basically, or primarily, a case of 2 counter-rotating "equal" vortices coming from the vortices of the wing tips of an airplane.

Extending this "definition" further, what is attempted in this Article is to know or model the interaction of various vortices, to know their past and future paths, knowing initial data (as in the case of Galaxy paths).

As it sees before, in Race Cars Engineering, we engineers have been studying for many years the interaction between Vortices created by ailerons (images of rear/front wing, by Jonas Pangerl and Marius Imiolczyk).

Meteorologists have assigned names (Crow instability) to these well-known vortices. They are still low-pressure "tubes" in which particles rotate.

The CFD techniques have a very useful tool, called "Core vortex", which perfectly points to the heart of the vortex, so as to analyze its path.

Vortex paths depend on many factors:

- Speed of rotation.
- Size.
- Sense of rotation.
- Density, Viscosity, humidity, etc.
- Of the paths of other vortices.
- But above all, pressure variations.

In this article, the CFD is pointed out as the tool capable of generating galaxies and observing their evolution and interaction with other galaxies, analyzing the interactions of the vortex cores of the vortices.

About the interaction between galaxies, it's very interesting to see to movement of tails; that it's normal, even necessary; in fact, the radio emission in center Abell 1775 (galaxy), observed by LOFAR (red) and placed in a optic image (Lofar / Pan-Starrs / Botteon et al. 2021):

In ([42] Peng Wang, Dr. Noam Libeskind, Sarah Hönig): "By mapping the motion of galaxies in huge filaments that connect the cosmic web, astronomers at the Leibniz Institute for Astrophysics Potsdam (AIP), in collaboration with scientists in China and Estonia, have found that these long tendrils of galaxies spin on the scale of

hundreds of millions of light years. A rotation on such enormous scales has never been seen before. The results published in Nature Astronomy signify that angular momentum can be generated on unprecedented scales”.

When a galaxy advances, it leaves, as seen in this work, a low-pressure trail. The low-pressure or low-density path will be larger (less density) if the galaxy:

- Is large.
- Has a lot of velocity.

When another galaxy encounters this low density tube, it starts to spin around the tube; this causes the paths of both galaxies to merge and grow; this can happen to many galaxies, so the pressure tube becomes very large. Many galaxies rotate around and inside the low-density tube; this effect is discussed in this article.

About these last points (A to F and more, I want to make some simulations CFD in order to corroborate every asseveration in every point:

- Create 1 or more vortices for analyzing:

“A” to “F”.

- **Spyder web or geometry universe in high scale**

The Background Microwave Cosmic (BMC), is a map of temperature variation in a distribution of mass in early universe (colors scale blue-red / low-high density or temperature):

Why this special final distribution or dynamic? This distribution of zones with more and less density is normal in the Nature. All explosions or blasts for example, not have an equal matter in any direction or point, fragments distribution, density or temperature (sun surface, supernovas, atomic bomb, nebulae, etc....):

The same occur in temperature in earth surface: there are little's variations:

2 ways or numeric models, for explaining this special structure:

- ➔ First way (simple method): it supposes that the Universe work as a fluid with density-viscosity (galaxies, environmental, etc):

These densities-viscosities variations (CMB), origin in the future, the different galaxies cluster and matter distribution in large scale. In fact, from this BMC as a boundary condition, is possible simulate the evolution of universe: the result is very similar to universe observable today:

➔ There are other way for creating the universe in high scale (more complex but more accurate):

For the formation of the web spyder or large scale structure of the universe, in a numerical modeling can be applied, Navier Stokes: with these equations, incorporating viscosity and external forces (such as gravity, magnetism, etc), it is possible to simulate the large-scale structure of the universe.

The speed of light, like the speed of gravitational attraction in the universe, depends on the environment. The speed varies depending on the density, viscosity, magnetism, etc.... This difference of "action" between particles, called now, Viscosity or difference of reaction time, is what produces the aggregation of matter-particles, forming the cosmic web.

This structure called “Spyder web”, is a Multifractal ([16] Vicent Martínez García).

It can also find this special geometric structure, in other field:

Abstract:

Predicting what is going to happen is very tempting, and it is something that everyone would like to be able to do, in an easy and above all reliable way.

Knowing a priori if it is going to rain in the next few minutes, while it is raining cats and dogs while having this desire is not something too difficult. However, knowing if it will rain in 46 and half days is not difficult at all. To know, for example, if tomorrow will be the day before, is easy, but it is not easy to know where a stone thrown with all the strength will fall.

In the determination or knowledge a priori of something, there are basically two aspects involved:

- The nature of the phenomenon itself.
- The time series we are using.

The essence of chaos is the scarcity and simplicity of laws that govern evolution; thus, it is easier to determine the evolution of the stock market than how a football will move; on the other hand, the more data we have about the evolution we want to simulate, the easier it will be for us and above all, the more reliable it will be.

In every chaotic process, there is a certain geometrical structure that is either visible or not observable: Fractal structure or geometry is the science that studies the representation of chaotic dynamics; we find fractal geometries in nature itself:

- Contours or borders of countries and coasts.
- The structure of a tree.
- The network of a person's blood circulation.

But also in representations of certain phenomena:

- The classic problem or simulation of a pendulum and 3 magnets of different colors.
- Etc....

One of the objectives that could be achieved by determining whether or not certain geometry is multifractal is to differentiate or classify phenomena according to their distribution of fractal dimensions.

Chaos:

The essence of the so-called "chaos" and of fractal and multifractal geometry, is precisely the scarcity and simplicity of laws: simple and scarce laws, originate structures of all kinds extremely complex and unpredictable; we only have to think that only one force, perfectly quantifiable, is responsible for the structure of the universe, with its galaxies and groups of galaxies, planets and planetary systems, etc. The fewer and simpler the primary forces that manage or describe a phenomenon, the more disorder and chaos there will be with respect to time and also space: for example, it is easier to predict the evolution of the stock market, than the evolution or dynamics of a fluid, the variations of a pendulum or simply where a stone thrown by us might fall. But also: the easier a problem seems to us, the more difficult it will be to find its foundation, laws and interdependence between factors, and the more difficult it will be to simulate its evolution in time.

Without chaos, there is no evolution, life or change of any kind.

This leads us to the statement of a new vision of chaos: the more unpredictable and the more difficult it is to solve a problem or a phenomenon, the simpler and more straightforward will be its foundations and the laws that govern it.

There is a very widespread concept or idea, which is directly or indirectly related to the concept of chaos or disorder; such idea is the so-called "butterfly effect". This idea is basically false or at least erroneous in its traditional concept; 2 events, causes or effects, are not necessarily united nor is it necessary for them to be dependent, even though it is said that they are in a very distant time or that their effects or inter-effects are appreciable in an infinitely small measure; it is essentially and conceptually false and erroneous. It becomes necessary, therefore, to define related and unrelated events.

How does the science of chaos help to explain such complex and different processes?

In recent times, the idea has been emerging that introduces the notion of chaos as a central element in research and in almost any scientific explanation or response. The idea of chaos and apparent disorder is a tool, which helps to understand certain phenomena that so far are almost inscrutable.

"The cosmos par excellence is the world, the absolute whole that contains all the partial alls," says Marcel Conche in "The Notion of Order," and disorder, adds Georges Balandier, "cannot appear except as a rupture of unity, of general harmony, and as an obscuring of purpose.

Chaos and disorder, as challenges to scientific thought, invite us to find the regularities of the irregular, the determinations of the indeterminate, the order of disorder.

Incongruent perhaps? We do not believe so. In recent times, this science that studies the relationship between chaos and the perceptible and non-perceptible world has been identified as "chaology". For Balandier, in his book: "The disorder", the chaology "seems to be concerned, at first, only in the curiosities or the deviations of the illusion in benefit of a science that has become strange. For her, triviality becomes mystery. The leaking tap is no longer a small domestic matter and a source of irritation, but the occasion for an erudite observation, made over the years, that makes this anomaly a kind of paradigm of chaos. The water of a waterfall, with its fall in layers, its dispersion in a multitude of droplets and its subsequent circulation towards the errant current, manifests a higher level of this complexity with a disorderly rhythm. Cigarette smoke, the companion to the wanderings of the spirit, which first rises in a straight line and suddenly twists and composes moving figures, suggests the presence of a similar phenomenon. Above, very high up, the marvellous clouds run, they construct celestial landscapes, mobile and always changing, chaos with which dreams are linked; but the new discipline wants to force its mystery, to find the answer that will make the forecast of the time beyond the immediate less fallible.

Chance is a determining factor in the manifestation of diverse phenomena and processes of the universe, and yet these are not as random as they appear or simulate:

Mitchell J. Feigenbaum, states that "we are full of chaos", beauty is "essentially chaotic", the shape of the clouds is also chaotic. The science of chaos is for him "the study of disorder, of the irregular behavior of deterministic things, those that you know how they behave from one instant to another, and yet their displacements become irregular, erratic, and give the sensation that they are produced at random. And in reality, what happens is that they don't happen by chance.

Julieta Fierro, comments that "in particular the transitions of the particles can be studied more adequately by resorting to chaos theory.

Thus, it is possible to conceive of other universes, parallel to ours and totally incommunicado, each with its very peculiar physics determined by chaos.... Thus the universe possesses order and disorder, cosmoses that form and expand and can give origin to symmetrical bodies like the galaxies with stars, ringed planets and life. The presence of chaos at all scales of the universe implies a great diversity of possibilities and, therefore, one or several universes with enormous potential to create diversity". In biology and medicine, chaos offers answers to problems such as issues related to blood circulation: turbulence breaks up circulatory and cardiac regularity. In the treatment of epilepsy, the creation of electrical turbulence in certain areas of the brain may be able to block or mitigate the attacks or convulsions caused by this disease or disorder. The applications that chaos can offer are immense: economy, stock market, political transitions, evolution of social conflicts, human relations, negotiations, etc...

Self-similarity:

One of the best-known geometries, perhaps because of its beauty and transcendence, is turbulence itself. Leonardo da Vinci (1500 A.D.), already described, in a truly masterful way, as it could not be less, which is the structure of a turbulence: "the small eddies are almost numberless, and large things are rotated only by large eddies and not by small ones, and small things are turned by both small eddies and large".

Who has not experienced, tested and observed the existence of personal problems, among the members of a group or team, and likewise, other types of problems in a subgroup of the main group, and so on? We have all dreamed at some time, that our society and ourselves, we are not more than integral part of another humanity or society formed by giants, as they are for example, the bacteria for us.

Something similar thought the ancients, when they said that the Milky Way in the night sky seen from the earth, was a trail of milk from the giants or gods; hence the name "Milky Way".

In fact, all fractals have the characteristic of self-similarity: any part is equal to the whole. We do not intend to make a course on fractals, since there are already articles and works on this subject. We simply wanted to offer this particularity that all fractals have.

The most usual representation of a turbulence is a spiral (everything depends on the parameterization that can be made of a phenomenon); it is as if the particles were attracted by a point (attractor), analogous to what happens in a sink, or as if the current lines are curled up on themselves around a point.

Every dynamic system has attractor points, understood as the points, states or times to which it is directed and evolves. If we parameterize a dynamic phenomenon in order to observe the current lines, the existence of a spiral (not zero rotational of the velocity field) will indicate the existence of turbulence. Under certain conditions, which are very easy to achieve, all dynamic phenomena governed by few simple laws, can cause turbulence; that is: under a potential context of chaos, it is easy to have turbulence or sudden alterations.

A few weeks ago, we found a series of photographs, specifically 4, in which the captions were wrong; the truth is that it was quite difficult for us to assign the captions to each one of them:

-
- Image from space taken to the vortexes created by the Island of Guadalupe.
 - A Karman vortex channel created by a soccer ball with $D=100$.
 - The distribution of galaxies within a cluster or group of galaxies and the distribution of stars within a given galaxy.

There are, and we are aware of this, many other phenomena, in principle different from all points of view, which are enormously similar in terms of their structure, representation or evolutionary dynamics. We find this structure or phenomenon, in situations so different, in scale, type or context, as: car wakes, sudden and chaotic alterations of the stock market or economy, turbulences in biological groups and information networks, internet, blocking of knots, politics, human relations, historical periods, medicine, psychology, meteorology, fluid dynamics, etc.

In short, turbulence is nothing more than "alterations or variations" with respect to, let's say, the "normal" of any type of dynamics; apparently, turbulence "twists" with respect to time (or to the chosen parameterization or representation); that is the essence of turbulence. This same "strange" or "abnormal" structure can also be found in other types of phenomena, not necessarily relative to the dynamics of a fluid.

An abrupt alteration of the stock exchange, for example, is nothing more than a turbulence caused by a series of initial and boundary conditions, which applied to a series of simple laws, originate a chaotic dynamic with respect to time. On countless occasions, after a bus has passed, we have related the turbulence it leaves behind to the results or alterations that certain economic policies, for example, leave in society.

The characteristic of self-similarity is shared by all dynamic phenomena, whatever their context.

Turbulent displacements are very common, both in nature (atmospheric flows, rivers,...) and in different applications of technological interest (flows in ducts, turbo machinery, boilers, combustion chambers, heat exchange equipment, vehicle aerodynamics,...), to the extent that most of the flows of interest, from almost any medium-serious or applicable point of view, are turbulent. The existence of turbulence alters various physical parameters of the fluid itself, as well as the flow itself.

For this reason, it is necessary to understand and comprehend its origin in order to be able to analyze and predict it.

The two scientific theories or methods could be said to be the most important and the most established, and par excellence, are radically different and propose extreme things:

- The existence of universal laws, which govern everything: a reductionist approach to science.
- The previous theory is not enough; to explain the world much more is required; from any level or scale, new phenomena appear, rich and varied, with elements absent in the previous, simpler level; new symmetries are generated and new forms of organization emerge; hence the need to generate theories for each phenomenon or even for each scale.

What is the real one? Perhaps, as is always the case in science and in knowledge in general, it is a mixture of booths.

Sir Horace Lamb (1849-1934), in an international tribute given to him on his eightieth birthday, in 1929, said: "When I die, I hope to go to heaven. There, I hope to be enlightened about the solution of two problems, quantum electrodynamics and turbulence. On the first, I am very optimistic..."

The first was solved by Richard P. Feynman (1918-1988), for which he was awarded the Nobel Prize in 1965. Feynman: "turbulence is the last major unsolved problem in classical physics".

Numeric model for calculating fractals dimensions (in order to know if it is fractal-multifractal):

Hausdorff's definition of dimension was introduced in 1918.

Let "A" a set of " \mathbb{R}^n "; the external measurement is defined α -dimensional of "A", as that: let " B_i " a coating of " A "; let " ϵ_i " the diameter of each coating and be an arbitrary epsilon.

$$B_A = \left\{ \{B_i\} / i = 1, \dots, \infty / A \subset \bigcup_i B_i / \epsilon_i \leq \epsilon / \forall i \right\}$$

We define external measurement α -dimensional of set "A", as that.

$$S_{\alpha, \epsilon} = \lim_{\epsilon \rightarrow 0} \inf_{B_A} \sum_i \epsilon_i^\alpha$$

For every "A" set, there is only one number "DH", named dimension Hausdorff of "A", DH(A), for which the following is verified:

$$S_{\alpha}(A) = \infty \quad \alpha < DH$$

$$S_{\alpha}(A) = 0 \quad \alpha > DH$$

The topological dimension of a set is defined as the number of coordinates needed to express a point belonging to that set. We can remember that a fractal is that geometric structure whose Hausdorff dimension is strictly greater than its topological dimension; given a fractal structure, we obtain from it a unique Hausdorff dimension. There are several definitions of Hausdorff's dimension applied to certain geometry; the most used method to calculate the "DH" is the box-counting method; this value, although it does not coincide exactly with the Hausdorff's dimension, coincides in the most interesting cases. The method consists of the following:

It place on the figure to be studied, in 2 or 3 dimensions, a rectangular grid with an epsilon " ϵ " amplitude; I count the number of cells in which the figure enters some box and I call it " $N(\epsilon)$ ". We repeat the experience for various values of reticular amplitude, and we place on a 2-dimensional graph, the values of " $\log(N(\epsilon))$ " and " $-\log(\epsilon)$ "; if we find the slope of the regression line that joins all the points found, we will have the dimension sought.

The problem arises when the set "A" to be studied is formed by points; it is true that we can also join these points by means of lines, and thus obtain a figure; but we do not intend to do this; we want to be able to study the discrete set of points, without having to generate another geometric figure from it. To do this, we need a series of concepts.

Let "A" be a set of points belonging to \mathbb{R}^n . $A = \{X_i\} / i = 1, \dots, n$. Let's give this set "A", a measure of probability. We will count for each " X_i " the number of points of the set that we find inside a sphere of \mathbb{R}^n of radius " ϵ ", with the center said " X_i ". I will call " $n_i(\epsilon)$ ", to this value. The probability that we will associate to each point of "A", will be the following one: $p_i(\epsilon) = n_i(\epsilon)/N$. In order that it is really a measurement of probability, we will impose the following condition:

$$\sum_{i=1}^N p_i(\varepsilon) = 1$$

By Jensen et.al.1985, we have that the probabilities are related to the radius of the sphere, through a law of powers:

$$p_i \approx \varepsilon^{\alpha_i}$$

The exponents “ α_i “, will be the characteristic exponents of the set "A". We can therefore consider the application that associates each point with its exponent: $V:Xi \rightarrow \alpha_i$; studying how these values are distributed, will give us a lot of interesting information when it comes to characterizing set "A", with respect to dimensionality.

A multifractal, is a fractal that has a distribution of characteristic exponents, instead of a single exponent.

That is: there are different zones with different fractal structures.

For each " B_i " covering of the "A" set, of epsilon amplitude, we can consider the following partition function:

$$\Gamma_1(q, \tau, \{B_i\}, \varepsilon) = \sum_i \frac{P_i^q}{\varepsilon_i^\tau}$$

" P_i " is a measure of the " B_i " set. To eliminate the dependence with " B_i " we make the limit of “ Γ_1 ” for "q" and " τ " less or equal to 0; if we call “ Γ_2 ” to this limit, we can define the partition function, as follows:

$$\Gamma(q, \tau) = \lim_{\varepsilon \rightarrow 0} \Gamma_2(q, \tau, \varepsilon)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Define } \Gamma(q, \tau) &= \infty \quad \text{if } \tau > \tau(q) \\ &= 0 \quad \text{if } \tau < \tau(q) \end{aligned}$$

$$\text{Define function: } \delta q: \delta q = (q-1) - 1\tau(q)$$

One of the reasons why this last definition is important, is $\delta 0 = DH$.

$$\Gamma(0, \tau) = \lim (\inf \varepsilon^{i-\tau}) / \varepsilon \rightarrow 0 \quad \tau \leq 0$$

If it change “ $\alpha = -\tau$ ”, it have:

$$\Gamma(0, \tau) = \liminf_{\varepsilon \rightarrow 0} \sum_i \varepsilon_i^\alpha = S_\alpha(A)$$

Since Hausdorff's dimension is unique, it follows that $\delta 0 = DH$.

The generalised dimensions of Renyi are defined as follows: Grassberger, 1983:

$$\lim_{\varepsilon \rightarrow 0} \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N p_i(\varepsilon) \log(p_i(\varepsilon))}{\log(1/\varepsilon)} = D_q(\varepsilon)$$

$$D_q(\varepsilon) = \lim_{\varepsilon \rightarrow 0} (1-q)^{-1} \frac{\log \sum_{i=1}^N (P_i(\varepsilon))^q}{\log(1/\varepsilon)}$$

These types of dimensions were introduced in 1983 by Hentschell and Procacia, as an attempt to define dimensions that were easier to establish relationships between them.

With the appearance of these dimensions, not only was this achieved, but also the dimensions used until then were defined, based on the generalized ones; dimension or capacity of Kolmogorov "DK" The following dimensions are available: the information dimension "DI" and the correlation dimension "DC".

$$DK = \lim_{q \rightarrow 0} D_q$$

$$DI = \lim_{q \rightarrow 1} D_q$$

$$DC = \lim_{q \rightarrow 2} D_q$$

The number of times "α" takes a value within the closed interval (α', α' + dα'), can be expressed as follows:

$$n(\alpha') d\alpha' = \varepsilon^{-f(\alpha)} d\alpha'$$

"f(α)", is the fractal dimension of the subset of "A" that have the same characteristic exponent "α"; that is: "V -1(α" where α ∈ (α' , α' + dα').

To draw the function "f(α)", we'll draw the envelope to the straights "y=qx-τ(q)", varying "q" from "-∞" to "+∞", (V.Martinez 1988).

The curve thus drawn has a single maximum and the value that the function takes at that point is the Hausdorff dimension of the set.

Very interesting things can be found in the works of P.Martien, S.Pope, P.L.Scott and R.S.Shaw on the time intervals between drops on a dripping tap in 1985, or the works of A.Provenzale, R.Vio and S.Cristiani on the variations of luminosity of quasar 3C-345 in 1993. From an apparently chaotic phenomenon in terms of its high unpredictability, we obtain a defined geometry, on which we define and calculate its multifractal dimensions. This characterization from the point of view of fractal geometry is applicable to other types of phenomena or time series.

The fractal dimension of a random distribution of galaxies is $D = 3$; the fractal dimension of galaxies located on the walls of low-pressure zones is $D = 2$; $D = 1$ on the walls, and $D = 0$, in galaxy clusters; in fact: $D(r)$ with distance r (Mpc/h):

$$\begin{aligned} D(0) &\approx 1.5 \\ D(0.8) &\approx 0 \\ D(3) &\approx 2 \\ D(100) &\approx 3 \end{aligned}$$

I have made an application – software in Mathcad, in order to apply it to dates (spatial coordinates, temporal series, etc....), and analyze the multifractal geometry characteristic (based in mathematic theory expose before):

$$\begin{aligned} h(n,j) &:= \text{if} \left[(x_j - px_n)^2 + (y_j - py_n)^2 < \varepsilon^2, 1, 0 \right] \\ R_n &:= \sum_j h(n,j) - 1 \\ p1_i &:= \frac{R_i}{N} \\ v &:= \sum_i p1_i \quad p_i := \frac{p1_i}{v} \\ \alpha_i &:= \frac{\log(p_i)}{\log(\varepsilon)} \end{aligned}$$

In this moment, it applies this procedure, in a Meteorites rain. That is: as a first sample:

It has a table with dates, each corresponding to the instant of sighting a Quadrantides (meteorites rain in 1992); the accuracy of the shots is the maximum achievable from the combination of the human eye, the brain, a paper and a pencil; the format of these shots is as follows:

- The first two decimal places correspond to the hour in universal time, the next two to the minutes and the last two to the seconds.

The table is composed of 303 time dates, and may be sufficient to obtain some information. For example: 0.015038.

In order to observe, analyze and draw some kind of conclusion about the moments of sighting,

it is convenient to normalize them by converting them into Julian time of day.

For this, assuming that in the data file, we have the moments already mentioned, and knowing that "a" is the year, "m" the month and "d" the day:

:=
C:\..\datos.txt

$i := 2..length(t) - 1$

$a_i := 1992$ $m_i := 1$ $d1_i := 3$

$fd1_i := floor(t_i \cdot 100) \cdot 60 \cdot 60$

$fd2_i := floor\left[\left(t_i \cdot 100\right) - floor\left(t_i \cdot 100\right)\right] \cdot 100 \cdot 60$

$fd3_i := floor\left[\left(t_i \cdot 10000 - floor\left(t_i \cdot 10000\right)\right) \cdot 100\right]$

$fd4_i := fd1_i + fd2_i + fd3_i$

$d_i := fd4_i \cdot \frac{10}{24 \cdot 60 \cdot 60} + d1_i$

d_j , is Julian day.

$d_j := floor(365.25a_i) + floor[30 \cdot 6001 \cdot (m_i + 1)] + d_i +$

$+ \left[2 - floor\left(\frac{a_i}{100}\right) + floor\left(\frac{floor\left(\frac{a_i}{100}\right)}{4}\right) \right]$

In this way, we can already work with this data, since it is already standardized and unified.

The geometric representation of the data we have is basic for a good analysis; and not only that: from certain geometry.

It will only be possible to extract certain information and not another one. It sees the different representations.

Let's see how the time intervals between each sighting evolve:

$dif1_j := dj_j - dj_{j-1}$

If it calculate the differences of a higher order and represent the evolution, it will obtain:

$$\text{dif2}_j := \text{dif1}_j - \text{dif1}_{j-1} \quad \text{dif3}_j := \text{dif2}_j - \text{dif2}_{j-1}$$

,etc.

The areas with the largest peaks correspond to the time intervals of least activity and vice versa.

This representation does not tell us much, except for what has already been mentioned; let's take the following representation:

$$j := 3.. \text{length}(t) - 1$$

This geometry tells us the rate of growth of the time intervals between sightings; that is: as time goes by, the frequency of appearance of a Quadrantides decreases.

Let us now take the n-order differences:

It has represented the differences of different orders, from consecutive values; we obtain analogous geometries, for non-consecutive values.

In this last representation-geometry, it applies the Multifractal theory.

Obviously, we could generate many more geometries, starting, for example, by substituting division, multiplication or whatever.

Another very useful representation is the three-dimensional one (even 4, etc....):

$$x(j) := dj_{j-1} \quad y(j) := dj_j \quad z(j) := dj_{j-2}$$

There is an Article ([38] Y. Brenier. U. Frisch. M. H'anon. G. Loeper. S. Matarrese. R. Mohayae. A. Sobolevski):

From the actual Universe in high scale, trough "reverse engineering", is possible create the early structure and mass distribution.

The formation of filaments is completely logical and normal. If a group of mass particles starts with a constant density and all of them with the same mass, no filaments will be formed, but that (initial distribution "constant and uniform" it's impossible (\rightarrow BMC – This BMC, it's a initial instability ;;;)):

There's a particular structure, called Laniakea:

The yellow surface represents dust (latest data from Rosine Lallement and her team), and the purple surface represents hot star concentrations (and traces the outline of the Local Bubble). No dark matter though.

In the particular case of the Laniakea, "attractors" are observed that are accumulations of matter, which produce a lot of gravitational attraction; on the other hand, there are "repulsors" or dipole repeller, which are the opposite (zones of low density of matter).

Therefore, it is necessary to simulate gravity, to have a good numerical model of the evolution of the Universe on a large scale; "?" is a dipole repeller point or zone:

The translation speed of galaxies today is not only explained by the existence of an attractor: a repulsive dipole is needed...:

The velocities of a galaxy can be calculated using gravitational fields. But we have to work with the possibility that the galaxies, in their paths, have been helped by the gravities of other galaxies or galaxy paths (gravitational aid). That is why the calculations, without working with this possibility, are incorrect.

It is necessary, therefore, that repellent dipole, but it is simply that it has less force of gravity or attraction, because it has less mass or density.

It is all a question of mass distribution and therefore of gravity: always attractive, never repulsive.

For example, in the case of a pipe, the fluid is expelled because there is a pressure difference: the fluid flow has a direction towards the low pressure. But this does not mean that at the other end, there is a "repeller" that pushes the fluid...:

Expansion of Universe models

Abstract

There are several numerical models, to explain how is the expansion dynamics, like the equations of Friedmann-Lemaître-Robertson-Walker.

But it is a model that is very simple to explain, for example, the variation of pressure or density, and other important values, and more: is only possible an acceleration negative. In this article new concepts and new procedures are defined, to obtain a more useful numerical models that are able to describe the dynamics of the Expansion of the Universe (positive or negative), as well as the evolution of diverse variables that participate in the phenomenon, as a variation density and pressure, and even the acceleration.

In these new created numerical models, expressions are established to calculate certain values of the intergalactic medium (such as density, viscosity, pressure, force), considering it as a fluid, which will be very useful in later articles, to know the evolution and interaction of matter in the Universe And other think more important: is possible other vision about Dark Energy, as force, not as a matter or particle. It describe expansion Universe model as a spring damper set, as energy from vacuum or low pressure and also and finally, from Navier Stokes equations.

Introduction

If it looks at the distances that separate us from the galaxies that are not in our local group, you will see that they are moving away from us. That is to say: the Universe is expanding.

Edwin Hubble already validated this fact experimentally by measuring the distances and speeds of many galaxies, and created a numerical model that expressed the linearity between distance “ x ” and speed “ V ”, whose constant is called the Hubble constant “ H ” ($V=Hx$). Recent observations have shown that this relationship is not linear, and some more important: the Universe is expanding with acceleration ($H=H(t)$). Why is it expanding and how? This expansion, will be end?

They are 3 very important questions that currently, do not have totally satisfactory or real answer. All explanations are hypothesis, which as such, must be demonstrated, and explain the reality.

One of the most accepted but not validate, is that there is a kind of dark energy, which works as the opposite of gravity, that is: repelling instead of attracting. In fact, the evolution of length parameter (“ a ”) in axis vertical, from big bang, against universe time in axis horizontal, from now: it’s possible see that from end inflation period to more or less 7500 million years, there are an acceleration negative, because the density was bigger than expansion force. From this date to actuality, surprise and Nobel prize so, there are acceleration positive (the gravity force was less than “dark force-energy”):

“H” is not constant in Time:

“a” scale universe factor (traditional nomenclature):

$$H(a) = H_0 \sqrt{\Omega_{R,0} a^{-4} + \Omega_{M,0} a^{-3} + \Omega_{K,0} a^{-2} + \Omega_{\Lambda,0}}$$

$$t(a) = \frac{1}{H_0} \int_0^a \frac{a' da'}{\sqrt{\Omega_{R,0} + \Omega_{M,0} a' + \Omega_{K,0} a'^2 + \Omega_{\Lambda,0} a'^4}}$$

Depending these values, it have one or other universe evolution, so is necessary know its....:

$$\begin{aligned} H_0 &= 67.3 \text{ km s}^{-1} \text{ Mpc}^{-1}, \\ \Omega_{R,0} &= 9.24 \times 10^{-5}, \\ \Omega_{M,0} &= 0.315, \\ \Omega_{\Lambda,0} &= 0.685, \\ \Omega_{K,0} &= 0 \end{aligned}$$

If $\Omega_{M,0} = 0.01$:

It's possible interpolate these lines, in this case, first sample and values:

$$a(t) \approx c_1 t^{2/3} + c_2 (e^{t/c_3} - 1)$$

$$c_1 = 0.822$$

$$c_2 = 0.0623$$

$$c_3 = 0.645$$

How to do the Excel sheet?

	A	B
1	Scale Factor Calculation	
2		
3		
4	Constants	
5	Omega R	9.24E-05
6	Omega M	0.01
7	Omega K	0
8	Omega D	0.99
9	H0	2.18E-18
10	Secs/gyr	3.16E+16
11		

					TIME	SCALE FACTOR
21					t	a
22	a'	f(a')	int(f(a'))	t	t	a
23	0	0	0	0.00E+00	0.00E+00	0
24	0.01	0.720918704	0.003604594	1.65E+15	5.23E-02	0.01
25	0.02	1.169293969	0.013055657	5.99E+15	1.90E-01	0.02
26	0.03	1.512911245	0.026466683	1.21E+16	3.84E-01	0.03
27	0.04	1.797985443	0.043021166	1.97E+16	6.25E-01	0.04
28	0.05	2.043648414	0.062229336	2.85E+16	9.03E-01	0.05

$$0 = A23 / (\text{SQRT}(\$B\$5 + \$B\$6 * A23 + \$B\$7 * A23 * A23 + \$B\$8 * A23 * A23 * A23))$$

$$0.003604594 = C23 + (A24 - A23) * (B24 + B23) / 2$$

$$0.00E+00 = C23 / \$B\$9$$

$$0.00E+00 = D23 / \$B\$10$$

“ ρ_m ” matter density, “ ρ_R ” radiation density, “ ρ_Λ ” dark energy density:

In green point, the matter attraction, win to dark energy; so the universe it expands (“ c ” speed of light, “ P ” pressure and “ ρ ” density):

$$P = w\rho C^2$$

“ a ” it’s a expansion factor (2 for example, means that the universe is 2 times bigger):

$w = 0 \rightarrow \textit{barionic - matter}$
 $w = 1/3 \rightarrow \textit{radiation - matter}$
 $w = -1 \rightarrow \textit{dark - energy}$

$$\rho(t) = \rho m_0 a^3 + \rho R a^4 + \rho \Lambda$$

Hypothesis

- Hypothesis 1: Non Homogeneous Universe.
- Hypothesis 2: Non Isotropic Universe.

Velocity against distance expansion model

In city traffic, when the speed of cars is bigger, the separation between the, also in bigger:

Today, we know that in Hubble expression $H=H(t)$; the expansion of Universe depend of a lot of things.

The “Expansion Velocity” may be, depend of Pressure and Density also (“x” space length), (“a” and “b” > 0):

$$V_E = \textit{function}(x, P, \rho)$$

$$V_E \propto \frac{1}{\rho^a P^b}$$

$$V_E = H(t) \frac{1}{\rho(x)^a P(x)^b} x$$

And more: is possible, a little variation of Hubble law:

$$V = H x^{1+\epsilon} / \epsilon \neq 0$$

Analyzing the possible error with “ ϵ ”:

If $\epsilon=0.01$, then (10^{26} meters \rightarrow radio universe):

$$\text{if } \rightarrow x = 10^{26} \text{ meters}$$

$$x^{2\epsilon} \approx 1.8(\text{error})$$

- **Vacuum acceleration expansion universe model**

Between 2 zones with different pressure, there is pressure difference which produces acceleration “a” (high to low pressure): pulling with acceleration “a” (“ ρ ” density, “P” pressure and “x” coordinate length):

$$a = \frac{1}{\rho} \frac{\partial P}{\partial x}$$

What is the origin of this Acceleration – Suction, as a Dark Energy action? It know perfectly, that the Bing Bang, is not an explosion or blast (is a space expansion). But, is perfectly possible to assign it an analogy with a wave-shock. In any wave shock produce by a blast (big bang for example), there are a zone of high pressure (wave front) and after, other wave or zone of low pressure. This zone, produce (without any drag) one acceleration: next images about wave explosion propagation with simulation CFD techniques (test made with Star CCM+ as a CFD code: simulation in 3D (cut plane view), 10 km diameter sphere, 14.5 million mesh cells, explosion of dynamite into air dry, K-epsilon turbulence model):

The front-shock wave, have only 2 brakes (drag): viscosity and mass (gravity).

It can see the low pressure rear in any car (any wave shock). The pressure profile in any blast wave is (the wave may to be oscillations (positives and negatives) in time). Friedlander waveform sample for any explosion:

The zone or zones, with negative pressure, the “dark energy”, work (the dark energy change in time), producing acceleration-suction (with positive pressure, work but pushing).

Even, combining some hypothesis is possible that in the future, there are variations positives and negatives in dark energy:

This evolution in waves or not, depend of densities in the universe (baryonic matter, radiation, dark energy, dark matter, electromagnetic, etc).

Applying the Euler Lagrange equations (“E” energy):

$$Kinetic E = \frac{1}{2} m \dot{x}^2$$

$$Potential E = m \frac{P_x}{\rho} x$$

So: $P_x = \frac{\partial P}{\partial x} = \dot{x} \rho = a \rho$

- *Navier Stokes expansion universe model*

This model of expansion of the Universe has been realized in 1 dimension, assuming that the whole Universe expands equally in any direction. But I don't think this is the case; there have been observations in various directions in the Universe, which show that it is not uniform in all directions (or equal); although there is little data from which to draw final conclusions, I think it is.

For this reason, the expansion of the Universe will depend on pressure and density, so in each direction, the expansion will be different. It works with Navier Stokes equations traditional.

Analyzing the expressions for every part in Navier Stokes equations:

Sup: $v = Hx$

$$\rightarrow \frac{\partial v}{\partial t} = H \dot{x} + H^2 x$$

$$\rightarrow v \frac{\partial v}{\partial x} = H^2 x$$

$$g = \frac{Gm}{x^2} = \frac{4\pi G \rho x}{3}$$

Viscous term:

$$\rightarrow \mu v = \mu H \chi$$

$$\rightarrow \mu \nabla^2 V = H \chi$$

The next term in Navier Stokes, is the most important:

$$\rightarrow \frac{P_x}{\rho} \quad \text{value ???}$$

Method 1:

$$\rho_{vac} = \frac{\Lambda c^2}{8\pi G}$$

$$P_{vac} = -\rho_{vac} c^2$$

$$\Lambda = \frac{3H^2}{c^2} \Omega_\Lambda$$

$$P = -\frac{c^4}{8\pi G} \frac{3H^2}{c^2} \Omega_\Lambda =$$

$$= -\frac{3H^2 c^2}{8\pi G} \Omega_\Lambda$$

Method 2:

It knows also, that:

$$\dot{\rho} + 3\frac{\dot{a}}{a} \left(\rho + \frac{P}{c^2} \right) = 0$$

$$P = \left(\frac{-\rho}{3H} - \rho \right) c^2$$

3 results for "P":

→

Derivating the expressions for “P” (in 2 methods).

→ Also: $H=H(x)$, from:

From Navier Stokes, directly:

Sup: $V=Hx$ (particular case):

$$\frac{P_x}{\rho} + g = \frac{P_x}{\rho} + \frac{4\pi G\rho x}{3} = H^2 x$$

$$P_x = \left(H^2 - \frac{4\pi G\rho}{3} \right) \rho x$$

It's easy calculating that, with other 2 models for “H”.

It's very interesting, the next expression:

$$P = \frac{1}{2} \rho V^2$$

→ From this special equation, and very common; it has a Navier Stokes equations part:

$$\frac{\partial P}{\partial x} = \rho V \frac{\partial V}{\partial x}$$

If the density is not constant:

$$\frac{\partial P}{\partial x} = \frac{1}{2} \frac{\partial \rho}{\partial x} V^2 + \rho V \frac{\partial V}{\partial x}$$

There is another problem, very important:

If the density or pressure is not the same in any direction or there are different densities in some places, if it calculates (from supernovas, or galaxies cluster or individual galaxies) the “ H_0 ” Hubble constant, the results can will be different.

That is very important, in the famous “Hubble Tension” problem: in the main Friedman equation, the “H” depend of density....

In this case, the density and/or pressure, can be a vector. Even the Viscosity....

- *Friedman equations expansion universe model*

Method 1:

Kinetic energy (T) + Potential energy “V” = E constant, so:

Sup: $V=Hx$

$$V = -\left(\frac{4\pi}{3} \rho r^2\right) \frac{mG}{r} = -\frac{4}{3} \pi G \rho r^2 m T = \frac{m}{2} r^{*2} \quad r=ax$$

$$E = \frac{m}{2} r^{*2} x^2 - \frac{4}{3} \pi G m \rho a^2 x^2$$

Dividing by ma^2x^2 :

$$\frac{2E}{ma^2x^2} = \left(\frac{a^*}{a}\right)^2 - \frac{8\pi}{3} G \rho$$

$$E = \frac{1}{2} m c^2 x^2 K$$

$$\left(\frac{a^*}{a}\right)^2 = \frac{8\pi G}{3} \rho - \frac{K c^2}{a^2} = H^2$$

Method 2.

Applying Navier Stokes equations, with $V=H$ (“g” gravity acceleration):

$$\frac{\partial V}{\partial t} + V \frac{\partial V}{\partial x} = g$$

In order to reach the correct value for critical density of universe, it’s necessary substituting “g” by “4g”; it’s necessary analyze that.... It’s possible may be, that this “4” was necessary in Navier Stoke equations applied to Universe expansion....

Method 3:

From Euler-Lagrange equations: Sup:

$$L = \frac{1}{2} m V^2 + \frac{GmM}{x}$$

$$\frac{\partial L}{\partial x} = \frac{8\pi G \rho}{3}$$

$$\frac{d}{dt} \left(\frac{\partial L}{\partial \dot{x}} \right) = \mathcal{X}^{**}$$

$$H^2 x + H^* x = \frac{8\pi G \rho}{3}$$

“H” constant:

$$\rho = \frac{3 H^2}{8\pi G} \quad \text{Critical Density.}$$

- *Spring-Damper expansion universe model*

Considering that the viscosity of universe works as a damper; also, the mass (gravity) and density so, work as a spring (in this special and particular case, not considering other's forces).

So (“KS” is a value of spring constant, and “KD” diffusivity of Damper) (is possible that “KS” and “KD” non-constants) (Vacuum(Force)=Fv):

$$F_v - K_S x - K_D \frac{\partial x}{\partial t} = ma$$

About the constants (in general form) (“F” and “g” functions):

$$K_S = f(\text{mass}, x) = f(m, x)$$

$$K_D = g(\text{viscosity}, x) = g(\mu, x)$$

It’s possible suppose that (reasonable option), is one option:

$$K_S = x$$

$$K_D = \text{Velocity} = V$$

Also:

$$K_D \frac{\partial x}{\partial t} = K_D V = F_{\text{viscous}}$$

$$K_S x = \text{Force}(\text{Gravitational})$$

Also, it’s possible substituting the acceleration “a” in the “Force” (generate by the “full” acceleration) general expression:

$$F = ma = m \frac{\partial V}{\partial x} = m \left(\frac{P_x}{\rho} - g \right) =$$

$$= H^* x + H^2 x$$

$$/V = H x$$

Very similar to Navier Stokes equations....

Applying the Euler-Lagrange equations:

$$L = \frac{1}{2} m \dot{x}^2 - \frac{1}{2} K_S x^2 + K_D \dot{x}$$

$$\frac{\partial L}{\partial x} = K_S x$$

$$\frac{d}{dt} \left(\frac{\partial L}{\partial \dot{x}} \right) = m \ddot{x} + K_S x$$

$$m \ddot{x} + K_S x + K_D \dot{x} = 0$$

With Navier Stokes equations and substituting Hubble equation ($V=Hx$), the importance of “pressure variation” as a dark energy, is more or less the importance of “ H^2 ”:

$$H^2 \propto \partial P$$

- *Equations and relations important*

The nomenclature and the definitions are the typical in Cosmology.

→ *Friedmann*

$$\left(\frac{\dot{a}}{a} \right)^2 = \frac{8\pi G}{3} \rho - \frac{K C^2}{a^2} = H^2$$

→ *Hubble relation*

$$H = V/x$$

→ *Acceleration (A) expansion*

Non relativistic matter → $P=0$:

$$V = \dot{a}(t) R$$

$$A = \ddot{a}(t) R$$

$$D = a(t) R$$

$$A = -\frac{mG}{D^2} = \ddot{a} R$$

$$\ddot{a} = \frac{-mG}{a^3 R^3}$$

$$\frac{\ddot{a}}{a} = -\frac{4}{3}\pi G\rho$$

Relativistic matter:

$$\left(\frac{\dot{a}}{a}\right)^2 = \frac{8\pi G}{3c^2}\rho - \frac{Kc^2}{a^2 R_0^2}$$

$$\dot{a}^2 = \frac{8\pi G}{3c^2}\rho a^2 - \frac{Kc^2}{R_0^2}$$

Deriving:

$$2\dot{a}a = \frac{8\pi G}{3c^2}\left(\rho a^2 + 2\rho a \dot{a}\right)$$

With fluid equation:

$$\frac{\ddot{a}}{a} = -\frac{4\pi G}{3c^2}(\rho + 3P)$$

$P > 0$, contributes to negative acceleration; $P < 0$, also contributes to negative acceleration.

→ Existence (it needs) of Dark Energy Λ

$$a = 0 \leftrightarrow \rho = 0 \rightarrow$$

$$\frac{a}{a} = -\frac{4\pi G \rho}{3} + \Lambda$$

→ *Attraction Force between 2 masses*

$$F = \frac{mM}{r^2} G$$

→ *Baryonic matter*

P=0 ; dust: dust gass; good model.

→ *Radiation*

$$P = \frac{\rho C^2}{3}$$

→ *Empty*

Lineal expansion:

$$\frac{a}{a} = \frac{-K}{a^2} \rightarrow a = \sqrt{|K|} \rightarrow K < 0$$

→ *Relation between “H” and “a”*

Matter baryonic:

$$\left(\frac{a^*}{a}\right)^2 = \frac{8}{3}\pi G\rho = \frac{8\pi G}{3} \frac{V}{a^3}$$

$$\left(\frac{a^*}{a}\right)^2 \propto \frac{1}{a^3}$$

Radiation:

$$\left(\frac{a^*}{a}\right)^2 \propto \frac{1}{a^4}$$

→ *Relation between “a” and “t”*

Only matter:

Method 1:

$$a = c t^p$$

$$\frac{a^*}{a} = \frac{p}{t}$$

$$\left(\frac{a^*}{a}\right)^2 = \frac{p^2}{t^2} = \frac{1}{a^3} = \frac{1}{c^3 t^{3p}} \rightarrow p = 2/3$$

Method 2:

$$\left(\frac{a^*}{a}\right)^2 = \frac{8}{3}\pi G\rho$$

$$a^{*2} = \frac{8}{3}\pi G\rho_0 \frac{1}{a}$$

$$\sqrt{a^*} da = \sqrt{\frac{8}{3}\pi G\rho_0} dt \rightarrow t=0, a=0 \rightarrow$$

$$\rightarrow \frac{2}{3}a^{3/2} \left(\sqrt{\frac{8}{3}\pi G\rho_0}\right) t$$

$$a(t) = t^{2/3} \sqrt[3]{6\pi G\rho_0}$$

The universe age, is younger so:

$$\frac{a^*}{a} = H = \frac{2}{3t} \rightarrow t = \frac{2}{3H}$$

Radiation:

Method 1:

$$\left(\frac{a^*}{a}\right)^2 = \frac{8}{3}\pi G\rho = \frac{8\pi G}{3} \frac{v}{a^4}$$

$$a = ct^p \rightarrow p = 1/2$$

Method 2:

$$E = \sqrt{m^2 + P^2} \approx P, P = \rho/3$$

$$\rho + 3\frac{a^*}{a}(\rho + P)$$

$$\rho + 4\frac{a^*}{a}\rho = 0$$

$$\rho + 3 \frac{\dot{a}}{a} (\rho + P)$$

$$\rho + 4 \frac{\dot{a}}{a} \rho = 0$$

$$\rho = \rho_0 \left(\frac{a_0}{a} \right)^4$$

$$\left(\frac{\dot{a}}{a} \right)^2 = \frac{8\pi G}{3} \rho_0 \left(\frac{a_0}{a} \right)^4$$

$$\frac{a \dot{a}}{a_0^2} = \left(\sqrt{\frac{8\pi G \rho_0}{3}} \right) t$$

$$t = 0, a = 0$$

$$a^2 \propto t; a \propto t^{1/2}$$

$$\frac{a}{a_0} = 2 \left(\frac{2\pi G \rho_0}{3} \right)^{1/4} t^{1/2}$$

H^2 total (baryonic + radiation):

$$\left(\frac{a^*}{a} \right)^2 = \frac{c_1}{a^3} + \frac{c_2}{a^4}$$

→ *Fluid equation*

Variation “Q” = 0; internal energy “U(t); density is energy density; “V” volume (sphere), and “P” pressure:

$$(*) \rightarrow dQ = dU + PdV$$

$$U(t) = \rho(t) * V(t)$$

$$U(t) = \frac{4}{3} \pi r^3 a^3 \rho$$

$$dU = 4\pi r^3 a^3 \frac{da}{dt} + \frac{4}{3} \pi r^3 a^3 \frac{d\rho}{dt} =$$

$$= \frac{4}{3} \pi r^3 a^2 \left(3\rho \frac{da^*}{a} + \frac{d\rho}{dt} \right)$$

$$\frac{dV}{dt} = 4\rho r^3 a^2 \frac{da}{dt}$$

Substituting in (*):

$$\frac{4}{3} \pi r^3 a^3 \left(\frac{d\rho}{dt} + 3 \frac{da^*}{a} (\rho + P) \right) = 0 \rightarrow$$

$$\rightarrow \frac{d\rho}{dt} + 3 \frac{da^*}{a} (\rho + P) = 0$$

$$H = - \frac{\dot{\rho}}{3(\rho + P)}$$

→ *Density and Velocity evolution*

$$dE = -P * dV$$

$$E = \rho V; dE = \rho dV + V d\rho = -\rho dV$$

$$V d\rho = -(P + \rho) dV; P = w\rho$$

$$V d\rho = -(wP + \rho) dV$$

$$V d\rho = -(w + 1)\rho dV$$

$$\frac{d\rho}{\rho} = -(w + 1) \frac{dV}{V}$$

$$d \log(\rho) = -(w + 1) \log(V)$$

$$\rho = V^{-(w+1)} = \frac{\text{constant } t}{V^{w+1}}$$

$$V = a^3$$

$$\rho = \frac{C1}{a^{3(w+1)}}$$

$$w = 0 \rightarrow \rho = \frac{C1}{a^3}; P = 0$$

$$w = 1/3 \rightarrow \rho = \frac{C1}{a^4}; P = \frac{\rho C^2}{3}$$

$$w = -1 \rightarrow \rho = \text{constant } t \rightarrow$$

$$\rightarrow H^2 = \frac{8\pi G}{3} \rho_0; P = -\rho C^2$$

$$H = \sqrt{\frac{8\pi G \rho_0}{3}}$$

$$a = a_0 \sqrt{\frac{8\pi G \rho_0}{3}}$$

$$a = \text{constant } t * e^{\left(\sqrt{\frac{8\pi G \rho_0}{3}}\right) t}$$

$$V = H * D(\text{Hubble}) \rightarrow$$

$$\rightarrow V = \left(\sqrt{\frac{8\pi G \rho_0}{3}}\right) D$$

If "V" is "c", then the universe age is between 10-12 billion years.

→ *Age of Universe*

$$H(a) = H_0 \sqrt{\Omega_m a^{-3} + \Omega_{rad} a^{-3} + \Omega_\Lambda a^{-3}} \quad t = \int_0^a \frac{da}{aH(a)}$$

$$V = H * x \rightarrow \text{length} = \frac{\text{length}}{\text{time}} \frac{1}{H}$$

$$\text{so} \rightarrow \text{age}(\text{today}) = \frac{1}{H_0} \approx 13.5 \text{By}$$

Schrodinger and Dirac equations

→ *Schrodinger equation*

From ([46] D. Cabrera, P. Fernández de Córdoba, J.M. Isidro, J.M. Valdés Placeres y J. Vázquez Molina):

$$i\hbar \frac{\partial \psi}{\partial t} + \frac{\hbar^2}{2m} \nabla^2 \psi - V\psi = 0.$$

It's possible:

$$\psi = \psi_0 \exp\left(S + \frac{i}{\hbar} I\right) = \psi_0 A \exp\left(\frac{i}{\hbar} I\right).$$

$$A = \exp(S)$$

Substituting:

$$\frac{\partial S}{\partial t} + \frac{1}{m} \nabla S \cdot \nabla I + \frac{1}{2m} \nabla^2 I = 0,$$

Real part and imaginary part:

$$\frac{\partial I}{\partial t} + \frac{1}{2m} (\nabla I)^2 + V + U = 0,$$

$$\frac{\partial S}{\partial t} + \frac{1}{m} \nabla S \cdot \nabla I + \frac{1}{2m} \nabla^2 I = 0,$$

$$U := \frac{-\hbar^2}{2m} \frac{\nabla A^2}{A} = \frac{-\hbar^2}{2m} [(\nabla S)^2 + \nabla^2 S].$$

$$\nabla I = m\mathbf{v},$$

$$\nabla(\mathbf{v}^2) = 2(\mathbf{v} \cdot \nabla)\mathbf{v} + 2\mathbf{v} \times (\nabla \times \mathbf{v})$$

The gradient of real part:

Obtaining the Navier Stokes equations:

$$\frac{\partial \mathbf{v}}{\partial t} + (\mathbf{v} \cdot \nabla)\mathbf{v} + \frac{1}{m}\nabla U + \frac{1}{m}\nabla V = 0,$$

In order to generate the Schrodinger equation: (“KE” kinetic energy, “PE” potential energy, “h” Planck constant, “f” frequency, “m” mass, “v” velocity, “P” movement quantity, “λ” wave length, 1 dimension “x”, “t” time:

- *Schrodinger Independent of time*

$$(*) \rightarrow KE + PE = \frac{1}{2}m\mathbf{v}^2 + V = E = hf$$

$$P = \frac{h}{\lambda}$$

$$E = \frac{P^2}{2m} + u / P = mv$$

$$\Psi = e^{i(kx-wt)}$$

$$\frac{d\Psi}{dx} = ik e^{i(kx-wt)} = ik\Psi$$

$$\frac{d^2\Psi}{dx^2} = (ik)^2\Psi$$

$$k = \frac{P}{\hbar}; k = \frac{2\pi}{\lambda}; P = \frac{\hbar}{\lambda}; P = \frac{\hbar k}{2\pi}$$

$$\frac{d^2\Psi}{dx^2} = -\left(\frac{P^2}{\hbar^2}\right)\Psi$$

$$-\hbar^2 \frac{d^2\Psi}{dx^2} = P\Psi^2$$

Substituting in (*):

$$E\Psi = \frac{P^2}{2m} + V\Psi$$

$$(**) \rightarrow E\Psi = -\hbar^2 \frac{d^2\Psi}{dx^2} + V\Psi$$

$$\frac{-\hbar^2}{2m} \nabla^2 + V(r)$$

$$H\Psi(r) = E\Psi(r)$$

- *Schrodinger Dependent of time*

$$E = \hbar\omega$$

$$\frac{-i}{\hbar} E\Psi = -i\omega\Psi = \frac{d\Psi}{dt}$$

$$E\Psi = \frac{\hbar}{-i} \frac{d\Psi}{dt} = i\hbar \frac{d\Psi}{dt}$$

Substituting in (**):

$$i\hbar \frac{d\Psi}{dt} = \frac{-\hbar^2}{2m} \frac{d^2\Psi}{dx^2} + V\Psi$$

- *Solution general Schrodinger equation*

$$\Psi(x,t) = \Psi(x)\varphi(t)$$

$$\left(i\hbar\Psi \frac{d\varphi}{dt} = \frac{-\hbar^2}{2m} \frac{d^2\Psi}{dx^2} \varphi + V\Psi\varphi \right) \frac{1}{\Psi\varphi}$$

$$i\hbar \frac{1}{\varphi} \frac{d\varphi}{dt} = \frac{-\hbar^2}{2m} \frac{1}{\Psi} \frac{d^2\Psi}{dx^2} \varphi + V = E$$

$$\frac{d\varphi}{dt} = \frac{-iE}{\hbar} \varphi \rightarrow \int \frac{d\varphi}{\varphi} = \int \frac{-iE}{\hbar} dt$$

$$\ln(\varphi) = \frac{-iE}{\hbar} t + \text{constan } t \rightarrow \varphi = e^{-iEt/\hbar}$$

- *Different cases and solutions Schrodinger equation*

See now, some different cases, working with operators in order to simplify the notation substituting the derivatives:

Case 1) $V(r)=0$

$$H = -\frac{\hbar^2}{2m} \mathbf{B}^2$$

$$-\frac{\hbar^2}{2m} \mathbf{B}^2 \Psi - E\Psi = 0$$

$$\Psi = \Psi_0 e^{iKx}; B = iK; \mathbf{B}^2 = -K^2$$

$$\left(\frac{\hbar^2}{2m} K^2 - E \right) \Psi = 0$$

$$\frac{\hbar^2}{2m} K^2 - E = 0$$

$$K = \frac{\pm \sqrt{2mE}}{\hbar}$$

Case 2) Potential step:

$$-\frac{\hbar^2}{2m} \mathbf{B}^2 \Psi - (E - V)\Psi = 0$$

$$\rightarrow K = \frac{\pm \sqrt{2m(E - V)}}{\hbar}$$

a) $E > V$:

$$\Psi = \Psi_0 \exp\left(i \frac{\sqrt{2m(E - V)}}{\hbar} x \right)$$

Less frequency and less $(E-V)$:

b) $E < V$:

$$\rightarrow K = \pm i \frac{\sqrt{2m|E - V|}}{\hbar}$$

$$\Psi = \Psi_0 \exp\left(-\frac{\sqrt{2m|E - V|}}{\hbar} x\right) = \Psi_0 \exp(\theta x)$$

The probability “ ψ ” of find a particle in the material, is less: but not zero !!!:

Case 3) Barrier potential: tunnel effect:

The amplitude and the energy “ E ” are less. Some particle, will go through the material; typical about the radioactivity particles:

Case 4) Well potential:

The particles are confined and some, can to exit:

Case 5) Wall potential:

The particle, cannot exit:

Case 6) Well with walls potential:

$$\Psi = B_1 e^{iKx} + B_2 e^{-iKx}$$

$$K = \frac{\sqrt{2mE}}{\hbar}$$

The two waves with the same amplitude:

$$\Psi(0) = 0 \rightarrow \Psi = B_1 + B_2 = 0$$

$$B_2 = -B_1$$

$$\Psi(x) = B(e^{iKx} - e^{-iKx}) = 2iB \sin(Kx)$$

$$\Psi(a) = 0 \rightarrow \Psi(a) = 2iB \sin(Ka) = 0$$

$$Ka = n\pi / n = 0, 1, \dots$$

$$B = \pm \frac{i}{\sqrt{2a}}$$

$$\Psi(x) = \sqrt{\frac{2}{a}} \sin\left(\frac{n\pi x}{a}\right)$$

It knows that:

$$K = \frac{\sqrt{2mE}}{\hbar} \rightarrow Ka = n\pi$$

$$E = \frac{n^2 \pi^2 \hbar^2}{2m a^2}$$

- Numerical solution Schrodinger equation by Crank Nicholson scheme discretization in 2D

$$i \frac{\partial \Psi(x, y, t)}{\partial t} = -\nabla^2 \Psi(x, y, t) + V(x, y, t) \Psi(x, y, t)$$

$$i \frac{\partial \Psi(x, y, t)}{\partial t} = -\left(\frac{\partial^2 \Psi(x, y, t)}{\partial x^2} + \frac{\partial^2 \Psi(x, y, t)}{\partial y^2}\right) + V(x, y, t) \Psi(x, y, t)$$

$$\frac{\partial \Psi(x, y, t)}{\partial t} = \frac{\Psi_{ij}^{n+1} - \Psi_{ij}^n}{\Delta t}$$

$$\frac{\partial^2 \Psi(x, y, t)}{\partial x^2} = \frac{1}{2(\Delta x)^2} [(\Psi_{ij+1}^{n+1} - 2\Psi_{ij}^{n+1} + \Psi_{ij-1}^{n+1}) + (\Psi_{ij+1}^n - 2\Psi_{ij}^n + \Psi_{ij-1}^n)]$$

$$\frac{\partial^2 \Psi(x, y, t)}{\partial y^2} = \frac{1}{2(\Delta y)^2} [(\Psi_{i-1,j}^{n+1} - 2\Psi_{ij}^{n+1} + \Psi_{i+1,j}^{n+1}) + (\Psi_{i-1,j}^n - 2\Psi_{ij}^n + \Psi_{i+1,j}^n)]$$

$$V(x, y, z) \Psi(x, y, z) = \frac{1}{2} [V_{ij}^{n+1} \Psi_{ij}^{n+1} + V_{ij}^n \Psi_{ij}^n]$$

$$r_x = -\frac{\Delta t}{2i(\Delta x)^2}, \quad r_y = -\frac{\Delta t}{2i(\Delta y)^2}$$

$$-r_y \Psi_{i+1,j}^{n+1} - r_y \Psi_{i-1,j}^{n+1} + (1 + 2r_x + 2r_y + \frac{i\Delta t}{2} V_{ij}^{n+1}) \Psi_{ij}^{n+1} - r_x \Psi_{ij+1}^{n+1} - r_x \Psi_{ij-1}^{n+1} =$$

$$= r_y \Psi_{i+1,j}^n + r_y \Psi_{i-1,j}^n + (1 - 2r_x - 2r_y - \frac{i\Delta t}{2} V_{ij}^n) \Psi_{ij}^n + r_x \Psi_{ij+1}^n + r_x \Psi_{ij-1}^n$$

$$a_{ij} = (1 + 2r_x + 2r_y + i \frac{\Delta t}{2} V_{ij}^{n+1})$$

$$b_{ij} = (1 - 2r_x - 2r_y - i \frac{\Delta t}{2} V_{ij}^n)$$

$$\begin{aligned} -r_y \Psi_{i+1,j}^{n+1} - r_y \Psi_{i-1,j}^{n+1} + a_{ij} \Psi_{ij}^{n+1} - r_x \Psi_{ij+1}^{n+1} - r_x \Psi_{ij-1}^{n+1} = \\ = r_y \Psi_{i+1,j}^n + r_y \Psi_{i-1,j}^n + b_{ij} \Psi_{ij}^n + r_x \Psi_{ij+1}^n + r_x \Psi_{ij-1}^n \end{aligned}$$

$$A \cdot x = b$$

$$\Psi_{0,j}^n = \Psi_{i,0}^n = \Psi_{N-1,j}^n = \Psi_{i,N-1}^n = 0$$

$$\begin{aligned} -r_y \Psi_{i+1,j}^{n+1} - r_y \Psi_{i-1,j}^{n+1} + a_{ij} \Psi_{ij}^{n+1} - r_x \Psi_{ij+1}^{n+1} - r_x \Psi_{ij-1}^{n+1} = \\ = r_y \Psi_{i+1,j}^n + r_y \Psi_{i-1,j}^n + b_{ij} \Psi_{ij}^n + r_x \Psi_{ij+1}^n + r_x \Psi_{ij-1}^n \end{aligned}$$

$$A \cdot x = \begin{pmatrix} a_{00} & -r_x & 0 & 0 & \dots & 0 & -r_y & 0 & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ -r_x & a_{10} & -r_x & 0 & \dots & 0 & -r_y & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ 0 & -r_x & a_{20} & -r_x & & & & -r_y & & & \\ 0 & 0 & -r_x & \ddots & \ddots & & & & & & \ddots \\ \vdots & \vdots & & \ddots & & & & & & & \\ 0 & & & & & & & & & & \\ -r_y & 0 & & & & & & & & & \\ 0 & -r_y & & & & & & & & & \\ 0 & 0 & -r_y & & & & & & & & \\ \vdots & \vdots & & \ddots & & & & & & & \\ 0 & 0 & & & & & & -r_x & & & \\ & & & & & & & -r_x & a_{(N-1),(N-1)} & & \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \Psi_{0,0}^{n+1} \\ \Psi_{1,0}^{n+1} \\ \Psi_{2,0}^{n+1} \\ \vdots \\ \Psi_{i,j}^{n+1} \\ \vdots \\ \Psi_{(N-1),(N-1)}^{n+1} \end{pmatrix}$$

$$k = (j - 1)(N - 2) + (i - 1)$$

$$\Psi_{ij}^n = \Psi_k^n$$

$$A \cdot x = \begin{pmatrix} a_0 & -r_x & 0 & 0 & \dots & 0 & -r_y & 0 & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ -r_x & a_1 & -r_x & 0 & \dots & 0 & -r_y & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ 0 & -r_x & a_2 & -r_x & & & & -r_y & & & \\ 0 & 0 & -r_x & \ddots & \ddots & & & & & & \ddots \\ \vdots & \vdots & & \ddots & & & & & & & \\ 0 & & & & & & & & & & \\ -r_y & 0 & & & & & & & & & \\ 0 & -r_y & & & & & & & & & \\ 0 & 0 & -r_y & & & & & & & & \\ \vdots & \vdots & & \ddots & & & & & & & \\ 0 & 0 & & & & & & -r_x & & & \\ & & & & & & & -r_x & a_{(N-3),(N-1)} & & \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \Psi_0^{n+1} \\ \Psi_1^{n+1} \\ \Psi_2^{n+1} \\ \vdots \\ \Psi_k^{n+1} \\ \vdots \\ \Psi_{(N-3),(N-1)}^{n+1} \end{pmatrix}$$

$$b = M \cdot y = \begin{pmatrix} b_0 & r_x & 0 & 0 & \dots & 0 & r_y & 0 & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ r_x & b_1 & r_x & 0 & \dots & 0 & r_y & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ 0 & r_x & b_2 & r_x & & & r_y & & & & \\ 0 & 0 & r_x & \ddots & \ddots & & & & & & \ddots \\ \vdots & \vdots & & \ddots & & & & & & & \\ 0 & & & & & & & & & & \\ r_y & 0 & & & & & & & & & \\ 0 & r_y & & & & & & & & & \\ 0 & 0 & r_y & & & & & & & & \ddots \\ \vdots & \vdots & & \ddots & \ddots & \ddots & r_x & & & & \\ 0 & 0 & & & & & r_x & b_{(N-3)(N-1)} & & & \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \psi_0^a \\ \psi_1^a \\ \psi_2^a \\ \vdots \\ \psi_k^a \\ \vdots \\ \psi_{(N-3)(N-1)}^a \end{pmatrix}$$

- Numerical solution Schrodinger equation by finite differences scheme discretization in 1D

→ Dirac equation

For me, one the best and prettiest equation in the world: all, from little idea....

$$\exists a, b / \sqrt{x^2 + b^2} = ax + by \rightarrow$$

$$\rightarrow a^2 = b^2 = 0; ab + ba = 0$$

That it's impossible with Number Real; but not with Matrices (Dirac idea $\uparrow\uparrow\uparrow$); with 1, 2 and 3 dimensions, not exist solution for this problem, but yes in 4 dimensions (there are others solutions, but this is typical):

$$a = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} b = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & -1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & -1 \end{pmatrix}$$

$$\text{Hamilton} \rightarrow E = \frac{P^2}{2m} \rightarrow$$

$$\text{Schrodinger} \rightarrow \left(i\hbar \frac{\partial}{\partial t} \right) \Psi = \frac{1}{2m} \left(-i\hbar \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \right)^2 \Psi$$

$$\text{Einstein} \rightarrow E = \sqrt{(pc)^2 + (mc^2)^2}$$

If:

$$P = i\hbar \frac{\partial}{\partial x}; E = i\hbar \frac{\partial}{\partial t}$$

Can originate problems with a double derivative (P^2) inside a square root: that, not a meaning physical; so, the Dirac idea in this case is; exist “a” and “b”?:

$$E = aPc + bm\mathcal{C}^2$$

Yes !!!!:

$$\left(i\hbar \frac{\partial}{\partial t}\right)\Psi = a\left(i\hbar c \frac{\partial}{\partial x}\right)\Psi + bm\mathcal{C}^2\Psi$$

Substituting:

$$E \begin{pmatrix} n1 \\ n2 \\ n3 \\ n4 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} m\mathcal{C}^2 & 0 & 0 & Pc \\ 0 & m\mathcal{C}^2 & Pc & 0 \\ 0 & Pc & -m\mathcal{C}^2 & 0 \\ Pc & 0 & 0 & -m\mathcal{C}^2 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} n1 \\ n2 \\ n3 \\ n4 \end{pmatrix}$$

The solutions for this system are the values of Energy; for that, it's necessary to calculate the eigen values:

$$E = \pm \sqrt{(Pc)^2 + m^2 c^4}$$

Are 2 values for the Energy; that is: 2 values for a particle: positive and negative; Energy negative ??? → 2 components (spin).

This expression, it's the origin for the antimatter....; the Empty, for Dirac, it's not empty: there are a lot particles with Energy negative (Dirac sea):

- The not existence of E negative, produce E positive.
- The not existence of charge negative, produce charge positive.